

Romanian Nationals Working in London's Night Economy: A Consequence of Europeanisation?

20,236 words

Candidate Number: VJSR4

SN 952145

9/4/2012

I have read and understood the UCL and Departmental statements and guidelines concerning plagiarism. I declare that: This submission is entirely my own unaided work. Wherever published, unpublished, printed, electronic or other information sources have been used as a contribution or component of this work, these are explicitly, clearly and individually acknowledged by appropriate use of quotation marks, citations, references and statements in the text. In preparing this coursework, I discussed the general approach to take with the person named on the cover sheet; however the content of the submission is my own work alone.

School of Slavonic and East European Studies
University College London

MASTER'S EXAMINATIONS
DISSERTATION COVERSHEET – PART 1

Please complete this form carefully and attach it to the cover of the **FIRST** copy of your dissertation before handing in to the Student Administration Office, Room 341.

Name of student: **IULIUS-CEZAR MACARIE**

Candidate number: **VJSR4**

Dissertation Supervisor: **Dr Ger Duijzings**

Degree Title: **MRes East European Studies**

Dissertation Title: **Romanian Nationals Working as part of London's 24 hour Economy: A Consequence of Europeanisation?**

Deadline for submission: **4th September 2012** Date of submission: **4th September 2012**

Declaration by student: **This dissertation is my own work. Quotations from secondary literature are indicated by the use of inverted commas and by reference to the author concerned. Literature used in this essay is indicated in the reading list placed at the end. I have been made aware of the UCL policy on plagiarism (<http://www.ucl.ac.uk/current-students/study/plagiarism/>).**

Signature:

RECEIPT OF DISSERTATION

Name (in CAPITALS please):

Received by:

Date:

Contents

Acronyms.....	3
Acknowledgements.....	4
Introduction.....	5
Literature review.....	13
A. Tracking Europeanisation in the lives of Romanian Citizens	13
Romania's integration in the EU.....	13
Europeanisation in Romanians' day-to-day practices.....	16
B. Theoretical explanations for night economy.....	19
World Systems and Migration Systems theories	19
Economic Anthropology explanations for capitalism, production and consumption	21
C. Empirical studies of night economy.....	27
Prevalence of night work in Great Britain	27
Effects on night workers	28
Methodology: Data and Methods	32
Introduction.....	32
Ontology and Epistemology	34
Data.....	36
Methods	40
Results	42
A. Socio-economic background and reasons to migrate.....	44
B. Being a Romanian working migrant living in London	46
<i>The working climate in Great Britain</i>	46
<i>The normality of day-to-day life in Great Britain</i>	50
C. Focusing on night work in London.....	52
Discussion and conclusions	60
Appendix One: Short Biographies of the Four Participants	65
Rică, the day student and night hotel auditor/receptionist	65
Leon, the barman 'traveller on this planet'	65
Mihai, the night city trader specialised on the Asian market.....	65
Cătălin, the night taxi driver	65
Appendix Two: Semi-structured Interview Questions	66
Semi-structured interview questions: addressed in Romanian and translated into English.....	66
References.....	67

Acronyms

EC	EUROPEAN COMMISSION
EU	EUROPEAN UNION
GB	GREAT BRITAIN
OECD	ORGANISATION FOR ECONOMIC CO-OPERATION AND DEVELOPMENT
UK	UNITED KINGDOM
UKBA	UNITED KINGDOM BORDER AGENCY

Acknowledgements

With greatest respect, I would like to thank the night workers who agreed to contribute to this study. They have kindly given their time and went out of their way to help with this work.

With equal respect I would like to thank my supervisor, Dr Ger Duijzings whom I met for the first time, in my first class, in the first year of the MRes. Then, I knew nothing about Anthropology of South East Europe. Now, I know I would like to learn more about this topic. He has been an inspiration. I knew even less back then that I will be night walking, night talking and night seeing. Thank you for infecting me with the *Nightlaboratory* virus. The virus is spreading ... London, București, Sozopol, Moscow, Sofia ...

Thank you to my good friend Michael, who has been commenting on my previous paper and with equal patience and insight, he did it again. Also, to Gareth who found the time to proof read it.

Abstract – This investigation explores the lives of four Romanian male migrants working night shifts in London's night economy, in an age of Europeanisation. The study follows in the tradition of anthropological research, with its preferred method of ethnographic fieldwork. The research departed from the diurnal ethnographic research and complemented it with nocturnal non-participant observations, coupled with semi-structured interviews. The projects aimed at capturing the lived experience and personal trajectories of four migrants travelling from Romania to work and live in London's night economy. It was decided to focus on London, a global city, offering maximum opportunities for nocturnal research and variety of jobs in the night economy. The sample was composed based on random selection method to ensure that all relevant dimensions and experiences were included, not for generalising concepts, but for enlarging a concept's reach. The evidence shows that the process of accession to the European Union in 2007, in the case of Romania, has created limited opportunities for Romanian night labourers in Great Britain due to restrictions of free movement of workers in the European countries.

Introduction

The year 2007 evokes a moment of great importance in the history of Romania because it marks their accession to the European Union (EU). The accession to the EU did not come with full membership as it did for the other eight¹ new member states which have joined the EU in 2004. This meant that nationals of Romania would face temporary restrictions on the free movement of workers in Europe. On 1 January 2012, however, Romania has entered its third phase of this seven-year transition arrangement. This phase lasts until 31 December 2013² when all restrictions against Romanians (and Bulgarians) must end after seven years. Despite the restrictions, within the five years since Romania's accession to the EU many Romanians imagined possibilities elsewhere than in their home country and travelled to other EU countries to earn money and live.³ In this respect, Andrei Pleșu⁴, former Romanian Ministry of Culture stated:

¹ This expansion wave of EU into Central and Eastern Europe included Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, Slovenia, Slovakia, the Czech Republic, Estonia and Hungary.

² Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Great Britain, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, and Spain (Spanish authorities have received approval from the European Commission to restrict access to its labour market to Romanian workers until 31 December 2012)

³ For statistics on how many Romanians have emigrated to work in countries of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) see International Immigration Outlook 2012 OECD report

⁴ Andrei Pleșu served as minister of culture after 1989 before working as a philosophy professor. From 1997 to 1999 he was Romania's foreign minister as an independent. He currently heads the New Europe College in Bucharest.

*'Who wants to live in a country like this? For my part, I feel burdened by the atmosphere created by the Romanian government'*⁵

More than five years have passed since Romania entered the EU, in 2007. The concerns highlighted by Pleșu are alarming and portray an image of unhappiness with the current social, political and economic affairs in Romania. The 2012 OECD report⁶ indicates that Romanians choose to leave their country to work and travel in other countries, and their numbers increase year by year. After the U.S., Great Britain (GB) is the second preferred destination for immigrants travelling to live and work into one of the 34 countries of Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries.

This study explores the lives of four Romanian male migrants working night shifts as part of London's night economy. It looks into the circumstances that led them to leave their home country and work in GB instead. By looking into their migration and work trajectories this research examines the routes they took on their travels to GB and if they had any economic and emotional support available on their arrival to GB or any help in obtaining night work. It further analyses the working climate in GB with a focus on the constraints the migrants face in terms of work restrictions mentioned above. This research takes an inter-disciplinary approach between Anthropology, Migration and European Studies. It aims to analyse certain processes: a) migration and work trajectories, and b) inclusion/exclusion of Romanian migrants in European (cultural, social, political and economic) structures and frameworks since Romania's accession to the EU. I aim to answer the following research question:

How has the process of EU accession in the case of Romania created opportunities for Romanian migrants in London's night economy?

⁵ Andrei Pleșu, 'A Brutal Assault: Democracy Loses as Romania Spins out of Control', *Der Spiegel* <<http://www.spiegel.de/international/europe/democracy-the-loser-in-romanian-power-struggle-a-843449.html>>

⁶ Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), *International Migration Outlook 2012* (OECD Publishing, 2012).

By relating the current debates on free movement of workers in the EU to the studies of migration and political economy, prevalent in migration studies and economic anthropology I focus my analysis on the migrancy and work trajectories of Romanians in the age of Europeanisation. Moreover, considering the public debates in Western European countries on the supposed inflow of working migrants coming from Eastern Europe and threatening to overtake the jobs of the people in the destination countries (i.e. GB) it is timely and acutely relevant to investigate the idealised notions of equal rights to travel and work in Europe against the realities of the day-to-day lives of Romanians traveling to work in London's night economy. Moreover, what I have not yet stumbled across in the 'intellectual landscape'⁷ theorising on migrant workers in Europe is an assessment of the impact of restrictions on the free movement of workers from Romania, on the backdrop of Europeanisation. This study is important since it is only by beginning to ask questions such as this that we begin to think about the consequences of processes, such as European integration, on the choices that people make when they have been limited to begin with. This is where I hope the study will make a contribution to fill the gap in this area, particularly as Romania approaches the end of 7-year transition period as part of the EU enlargement programme/strategy.

We approach a night society that is based on a night economy where night workers share the social space of the night – 'a social space that is highly structured and inherently subversive, as transnational as it is transgressed, and shot through with inequalities of power.'⁸

As we move towards a night society⁹ the frontier between day and night becomes less visible. The capitalist economies blend day and night shifts, and as it expands to faraway places more

⁷ Les Back, *The art of listening* (Oxford: Berg, 2007), p. 176.

⁸ Russell Leigh Sharman and Cheryl Harris Sharman, *Nightshift NYC* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2008), p. 3.

⁹ Leon Kreitzman, *The 24 hour society : transforming time in our lives* (London: Profile, 1999).

and more people imagine fulfilling their possibilities in cities other than the ones where they were born. London, as a 'global city' with a night economy needs maintenance around the clock and attracts migrants who choose to travel to work and live abroad. Global cities like London are similar to satellites situated around the planet that run the entire world economy. In these urban megalopolises there are concentrated highly skilled workforces in key fields of the globalised economies (e.g. banking, finance, marketing and advertising, consulting and high-technology production centres). Also, in these cities that refuse to sleep there are service sectors running day and night to sustain the pulse of these places running nights.

Night is a natural phenomenon; night work is not. It goes back to Roman times and the number of night workers has increased during the Industrial Revolution.¹⁰ Night workers are split into full-time permanent night workers – regularly working between 18:00-06:00; In GB, there are over 300,000 people working nightshifts. Labour Force Survey data show the 1,059,992 of British night workers is made of these categories: 'three-shift working, continental shifts, sometimes nights/day and nightshift.'¹¹ However, there is no data on Romanian migrant night workers in GB.

This study follows Massey and colleagues' argument that capitalist economic relation penetrating the noncapitalist societies 'create a mobile population that is prone to migrate abroad'¹² from peripheric societies to core regions of capitalist societies. I explore this point in greater detail in the literature review by adopting World and Migrations Systems perspectives.

¹⁰ Will Norman, 'Rough Nights: The Growing Dangers of Working at Night', (Young Foundation, 2011).

¹¹ Ibid, p. 7. For details on the Labour Force Survey data see Appendix 4

¹² D. S. Massey and others, 'Theories of International Migration - A Review and Appraisal', *Population and Development Review*, 19 (1993), 444.

Within the tradition of economic anthropology there is an inclination to Marxism, which I adopt here in order to analyse capitalist societies in terms of production and expansion. Here, I aim to clarify central concepts such as, 'mode of production' (MoP) to explain the struggle between the classes of people, i.e. the propertied individuals exploiting 'means of production' against the weak and, the subordinated wage-labourers, such as night workers striving to survive under the ruling class.

I have chosen Romanian migrants for a number of reasons, some more subjective than others. Easier access to data in Romanian, speaking the same language as the participants, and having lived in Romania during the ten years post-revolution transition may have played a role. Secondly, and more objectively, Romania presents an interesting case due to the fact that its accession to the EU did not entitle it to full membership and its nationals to free movement of work in all European countries.¹³

The participants in this study have chosen to travel for work and currently live in GB. Therefore, I find it relevant to consider Laura Agustín¹⁴ anthropologic standpoint, who thinks that migrancy is 'a process and not an identity or label', such as 'migrant domestic worker.'¹⁵ 'At its best, 'migrancy is a temporary identity'¹⁶ or a phase in the travellers' lives. One could connect with the fact that night workers are in fact in transition, working only for a period, due to constraints and necessities. The travellers have a process, not an identity, in common, a

¹³ For a comparison between rights of free movement of workers for EU nationals and Bulgarians and Romanians workers see Appendix 5

¹⁴ She is an anthropologist and long-time migrant whose work situates her within the fields of migration, labour markets and sex industry.

¹⁵ Laura María Agustín, *Sex at the margins : migration, labour markets and the rescue industry* (London ; New York: Zed Books, 2007), p. 10.

¹⁶ Ibid, p. 10.

point which I embrace as it is relevant to the migration experiences of the participants in this study. First, it is relevant because they have left their countries and they need to earn money to live in GB. Second, some participants could not afford the money to pay for their travel and they accumulated debts. Those who lend the money, in some cases, are family members or old friends. During their migrancy, migrants may run into what Agustín calls debt bondage or slavery – ‘the debt that migrants contract is often referred to as bondage or slavery, but not all debts are alike and not all require working in a specific place or in oppressive conditions.’¹⁷

By applying however, Teresa Gowan’s qualitative approach, I combined participants’ words, field notes, and my observations to portray their voices, descriptions and evidence coming through the unfolding lives of these four male night workers. This study tells their stories of sacrifice and vulnerability, about overcoming difficulties to fulfil their imagined possibilities and aspirations. Finally, it shows how night work affects their social and family lives.

This study aims to show evidence that due to circumstances, such as Romania’s accession to the EU (European Union) in 2007, the continuing social and economic decay, and the imagined possibilities abroad (i.e. GB) young males are determined to travel abroad and, work nightshifts despite its negative consequences in order to fulfil their professional or personal aims. By giving voice to the individual experiences of Romanian migrants working nights in GB, this research adds a new dimension to the existing academic studies on night phenomena in close relation to a social field hardly ever associated, namely Europeanisation.

¹⁷ Ibid, p. 34.

The findings demonstrate that only one in four participants was constrained and pushed into taking night work for one year in order to fulfil GB Border Agency criteria to allow him to work in Britain without any restrictions, i.e. not being constrained to work a maximum of 20 hours per week as it is the case. Moreover, none of the participants worked nights in their pre-migration working lives and they did not have any intentions to work nights on a long-term basis.

The study also corroborates similar evidence from previous research carried out on night workers in GB, and highlights that the number of negative consequences outweigh the positive ones. The participants who felt most disadvantaged claimed to have problems with isolation and danger of being attacked during night shifts. While on a regular graveyard shift, one participant claimed that after a few months he felt mentally and physically strained. At the light end of the scale, participants unanimously echoed each other in terms of having restricted social lives, especially during the week because they could not join friends or day-time colleagues for a drink as these always occurred before their nightshifts.

In the literature review I will discuss the theoretical and empirical bodies of work in which I embedded my research questions. I identified and grouped the arguments in the following order: (A) debates on Europeanisation and Romania's accession to the EU, followed by (B) theoretical explanations for the night economy and (C) empirical studies of the night economy.

The methodology chapter will describe my ontological and epistemological (anti-foundationalist position), and explain how they shaped my research practice anchored in anthropological theory and its ethnographic method of non-participant observation

complemented with semi-structured interviews. Then, I will describe the findings in the results chapter, followed by a discussion and analysis of the main findings. I conclude with some remarks on the implications of this study and modest proposals for future research possibilities.

Literature review

This chapter introduces the theoretical frameworks from perspectives of European Studies, Migration Studies and Economic Anthropology with a Marxist inclination. In doing so, the literature review aims to connect the research question, both theoretically and empirically to a larger body of research.

A. Tracking Europeanisation in the lives of Romanian Citizens

In the context of EU enlargement and that of free movement of workers from the new member states, Europeanisation is reflected in the parameters set by the European Commission as conditions that need to be met prior to accession into the EU. Of relevance to this study are the transitional provisions for enlargement in terms of restrictions to free movement of workers applied to new countries, i.e. workers from Romania (and Bulgaria) are subject to work restrictions when residing in old member states of the EU, for up to 7 years. Olsen's simplified definition of Europeanisation depicts an intertwining process geared towards: a) growth of the European identity, b) formation and enlargement of the EU, and c) exporting European powers behind its continental borders.¹⁸ Of particular interest here is the way in which the fifth EU enlargement happened in 2004 followed by the one in 2007, which I discuss next.

Romania's integration in the EU

The fifth enlargement of the EU, in 2004, included eight European states (A8). Romania and Bulgaria followed in 2007 but, not as members with full membership that is they were not included in the Schengen area and its nationals are restricted to work freely in the old member states for up to 7 years. For the purpose of this study I focus only on Romania's accession to the EU. The grounds for delaying its entry into the EU were that Romania

¹⁸ Johan P. Olsen, 'The Many Faces of Europeanization', *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 40 (2002).

needed to secure its external borders against those who, 'as non-EU citizens, posed a threat to this borderless territory.'¹⁹

Bojkov argues that in 2004 Romania was 'neither here, nor there'²⁰ in the European politics of that time.²¹ In other words, it was neither full member of the EU nor forming an integral part of the countries in the South Eastern Europe region. But one thing stands out for me, and Bojkov does not mention it. By inviting Romania to join EU in 2007 without full membership rights EU has made a mistake, which has repercussions visible today, five years after its accession. Keith Vaz, Labour MP (Member of Parliament) explained to me,²² on one hand, nationals of new member states cannot enjoy the full rights of being in the EU, i.e. Romanians are restricted to work legally in countries like GB. On the other, not allowing Romanians to work damages GB's economy, because, he says, the government loses money from not getting the taxes and national insurance from these Romanian nationals who would otherwise pay.

The UK Border Agency (UKBA) issues work permits to Swiss, EEA, and EU nationals. Romanians (and Bulgarians) however, prior to obtaining a work permit in GB, they need to apply for an *accession worker card*, which entitles these EU citizens to work in GB. They can obtain it only if an employer has been successful in their application for a work permit on their behalf.²³ Alternatively, Romanians and Bulgarians wishing to work as self-employed can apply at job centres for National Insurance Numbers, and do not need work permits.

¹⁹ Ginette Verstraete, *Tracking Europe: Mobility, Diaspora, and the Politics of Location* (Durham and London: Duke University Press, 2010), p. 94.

²⁰ Victor D. Bojkov, 'Neither Here, Not There: Bulgaria and Romania in Current European Politics', *Communist and Post-Communist Studies*, 37 (2004).

²¹ *Ibid.*, p. 512.

²² Comments to the author on 30.08.2012, Mr. Vaz has been a Minister for Europe in the period of 1999-2001 and was involved in the negotiations for Romania's accession to the EU.

²³ UK Border Agency, 'Bulgarian and Romanian nationals', *UK Border Agency*
<<http://www.ukba.homeoffice.gov.uk/eucitizens/bulgaria-romania/>>

Another category of Romanian citizens who do not need an *accession worker card* are seasonal (agricultural) and low-skilled workers in GB's food manufacturing.

Yet, Romanian students in British universities are required to have a work permit, known as *yellow card*. This allows them to work maximum of 20 hours per week during term-time and full-time during summer holidays. Romanian students face long waiting lists of up to eight months from the date of application for a work permit. As Keith Vaz, MP declared recently to a reporter from '*Român in UK*':

*'It is intolerable, that the Romanian citizens must wait seven months and a half to obtain work permits in Great Britain. Romanian citizens are EU citizens and they should be offered the same courtesy as the other EU citizens ... The Romanian students from British universities are the ones affected the most.'*²⁴

Anca Pușcă however, argues that Romania 'has faced one of the most difficult transitions to capitalism, which makes Romania an interesting case-study for its transition trajectory.'²⁵ Put differently, Romania's transition meant moving towards liberal democracy and market economy, meeting the exclusive benchmarks of the EU whilst fighting an enduring problem for Romania, i.e. corruption of the high-ranking officials.²⁶ The fact that Romania has been lagging behind, as often accused by the European Commission's (EC), comes from Andreev's, Racoviță's and Pușcă's analyses which show that so far Romanian government

²⁴ Român in UK, 'A British Member of Parliament says it! 'O spune un parlamentar britanic!' ', *Român in UK* <<http://romaninuk.net/index.php>>

²⁵ Anca Mihaela Pusca, *Revolution, democratic transition and disillusionment : the case of Romania* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2008), p. 3.

²⁶ European Commission, 'Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council. On Progress in Romania under the Cooperation and Verification Mechanism.', (Brussels: European Commission 2008).

has been impotent in eradicating corruption²⁷, protecting democracy²⁸ and 'enforcing and managing reforms as well as in its willingness to accept the new capitalist ideals.'²⁹

Concerns about the social decay in Romania come also from intellectuals like Pleșu who lives in Romania and points out that five years have passed since its accession to the EU, and Romanian government cannot ensure the minimum necessities for everyday life, namely, creating humane conditions for its people to work and live in prosperity.³⁰ When one takes in account the above analyses however, what one finds is that Romanian people assess the situation for what it is and decide to travel abroad to earn money and live. In the next sub-section I analyse how Europeanisation renders into the Romanian citizens' day-to-day practices, such as free movement to work beyond the borders of their countries.

Europeanisation in Romanians' day-to-day practices

In this sub-section I illustrate the paradoxes between idealised notions of freedom of movement in Europe in contrast with the realities of day-to-day lives of working migrants. Two of the day-to-day practices in the lives of people are travel (mobility) and work. For the purpose of this investigation the onus is on the workers travelling between home and destination countries for the sole purpose of working and earning money abroad. In contrast to Agustín who concentrates on the process³¹, Verstraete describes this category of migrants as those who travel in the opposite direction of capital from lower income countries like Romania, 'making use of existing networks of labour movement into Europe rather than seeking rights and prosperity at home.'³²

²⁷ Mihaela Racoviță, 'Europeanization and Effective Democracy in Romania and Bulgaria', *Romanian Journal of Political Science*, 11 (2011), 28-49.

²⁸ Svetlozar A. Andreev, 'The Unbearable Lightness of Membership: Bulgaria and Romania After the 2007 EU Accession', *Communist and Post-Communist Studies*, 42 (2009), 375.

²⁹ Ibid, p. 3.

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ Ibid, p. 10.

³² Ibid, p. 11.

Theoretically, having acquired European citizenship - Romanians should have rights to freely travel and work in any European country. In day-to-day practice however, the work restrictions still exist despite their transitory nature, i.e. according to the Treaty of Nice they should have been ceased in 2011. Some of the old member states have re-confirmed in January 2012 that work restrictions will be in force against Romanians till 31 December 2013.³³ This predicament makes Romanian nationals vulnerable in several ways, two of which I illustrate below.

Mr Vaz, MP explained to me that not giving full membership to Romania at the point of entry into the EU was a mistake that hopefully EU has learnt from. It has created opportunities for the old member states to prevent Romanians accessing their labour markets and thus making these nationals vulnerable and open to exploitation.³⁴ An example, he explains, is the way in which UK Border Agency (UKBA) deals with Romanian nationals. Some are students at British Universities and are prevented from working part or full time due to intolerable delays and waiting times of up to eight months in issuing them with a student work permit. He is not certain if Romanian nationals face this problem due to the incompetence of UKBA or because they do it deliberately to stop Romanians to work in this country at a time when the current economic climate is causing more and more British to lose their jobs. But this problem needs sorting out.

Although the following example is not related to night work, is acutely relevant in terms of infringements on the rights to free movement of workers from Romania. More, it demonstrates how vulnerability can sip into the day-to-day working lives of Romanians without protection from EU, Romanian institutions (e.g. Romanian Embassy) or under the

³³ Balkan Insight, 'EU to Set Restrictions for Bulgaria, Romania Workers', *Balkan Insight* <<http://www.balkaninsight.com/en/article/ec-to-announce-restrictions-on-bulgaria-romania-workers>> [accessed 25 April 2012]

³⁴ Comments to the author, 30.08.2012

responsibility of an employer in GB. I conducted field observations of a strategic venue in North London, where migrant workers congregate at the beginning of the day and hang out by the road, waiting for potential employers. Due to Romanians standing together with non-EU citizens (and possibly illegal in this country) they were treated with equal suspicion by the authorities. Romanians were vulnerable to random Local Authority checks, which endorse Police Dispersal Orders enforced under the Immigration Asylum and Nationality Act 2006.³⁵ This meant that some of the Romanian migrants risked of being charged with Anti-Social Behaviour Orders - a policy applied by the Local Council, usually enforced against assault and similar violent behaviour. Equally controversial, as I learnt, is that Section 15 should only be enforced in cases where those persons were subject to the Immigration Law Status, i.e. citizens of non-EU countries whose residence status was under review by UKBA. But as far as I was told Romanians present there were not subject to immigration dispute, yet they were removed from this site as I have witnessed on two occasions.

Nevertheless, the Free Movement Directive of EU applies since April 2006³⁶ and stipulates that any EU citizen travelling with valid documents has the right to reside in another member state of the EU for up to three months and longer if they have health insurance and enough financial means to live without applying for social benefits in the destination member state. Romanians travelling within the EU are doing as the EU directive stipulates: they take the opportunities offered to find equal rights and prosperity abroad. Some plan to live there for longer than three months and others go back and forth.³⁷

³⁵ The law on preventing illegal working is set out in sections 15 to 25 of the Immigration, Asylum and Nationality Act 2006. These rules came into force on 29 February 2008. These rules are in place to make it harder for people with no right to work in the UK to unlawfully gain or keep employment

³⁶ Peter Vermeersch, 'Roma and Mobility in the European Union', in *Roma and Traveller Inclusion in Europe. Green Questions and Answers.*, ed. by Kati Pietarinen (Belgium: Green European Foundation and Finnish Green Cultural and Educational Centre, Visio, 2011), pp. 91-97.

³⁷ Ibid.

In summary, the paradoxes that I discussed are reflected in the differential treatment of people travelling from lower income countries like Romania due to restrictions to freedom of work in other EU countries in contrast to the idealised notions of equal rights to free movement for all EU citizens.

B. Theoretical explanations for night economy

This section aims to offer some explanations as to why Romanian migrants decide to travel abroad for work and what are the determining factors. The first part analyses what creates the flows of migrants travelling from the peripheric societies to the core ones adopting the paradigm of World and Migration Systems theories. The second part aims to describe society from the perspective of economic anthropology with a Marxist inclination. The final part looks at the prevalence of night work in GB and at the negative and positive effects this has on night workers. The first two parts offer a theoretical paradigm to understand how globalisation and capitalism expanded during the last three decades into a new night world of production, consumption and exchange. The last part draws on empirical studies of the night economy. World Systems and Migration Systems theories will be discussed next.

World Systems and Migration Systems theories

Migration and World systems explain that when capitalist societies expand into non-capitalist societies residents are prone to migrate abroad. In the same vein as Verstraette's argument, Massey and colleagues confirm that people migrate in the opposite direction of capital for several reasons. Moreover, Massey and colleagues argue that World System and Migration System theories explain *why* migration is initiated rather than *how* it is perpetuated. *Why* people migrate is the question I aim to answer in this sub-section and I find it relevant to apply these two theories to this study.

Massey and colleagues identified that the aim of the expansionist capitalist economies of the *receiving* countries from Western Europe, North America, Oceania and Japan is the incorporation of the rest of the world and human population within the world market economy,³⁸ 'taking advantage of the low wage rate', and controlling the newly created markets for their products.³⁹

Of similar theoretical relevance is the explanation put forward by Fawcett and Zlotnik. They argue that 'an international migration system generally includes a core *receiving* region, one or more countries, and a set of specific *sending* countries linked to it by unusually large flows of immigrants.'⁴⁰ The evidence I presented in Appendix 2 suggests that Romania is on the second place after China in terms of *sending* countries to core regions, such as the U.S. and GB. The evidence also shows that the number of Romanians leaving abroad increases with each year. If we were to take in account these trends of immigration flow of migrants from sending countries like Romania to receiving countries (i.e. OECD countries) one would argue that explanations given by Fawcett and Zlotnik help understanding of how international migration systems ... This explanation is incomplete for the fact that it is not as specific as Sassen's analysis. Sassen analysed of the international investment and labour flow exposes that this is the case when international capital coming from the *receiving* (developed) countries causes disruptions in *sending* (developing) countries resulting in the population of that country emigrating in search for prosperity abroad.⁴¹ As some of the respondents in this study comment, the political instability, corruption, lack of economic progress and jobs in

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ Ibid, p. 445.

⁴⁰ J. T. Fawcett, 'Networks, Linkages, and Migration Systems', *International Migration Review*, 23 (1989).

⁴¹ Saskia Sassen, *The Mobility of Labor and Capital: A Study in International Investment and Labor Flow* 1st paperback edition. edn (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1988).

Romania has contributed to their decision to leave the country and search for prosperity abroad.

However, the mobility of people in reverse direction of capital is not the only way that globalisation has affected space and time. But, before I try to do the unravelling, which will allow me to move towards Appadurai's idea of migration through the *work of imagination*, let me review where we have been.

World Systems theorists, such as Massey and others invite us to believe that there is a *core* and *periphery*⁴² and hypothesize that all migration is a cause of disruptions and dislocations. Moreover, Fawcett⁴³, Zlotnik⁴⁴ and Sassen⁴⁵ are more specific about the flow of labour which they claim that goes in the opposite direction of capital from *sending* to *receiving* countries. Although, in their evaluation of migration theories Massey and colleagues do not exclude this and other explanations (*network*, *institutional* and *cumulative causation*) they point out however, that international migration has less to do with differentiation between *sending* and *receiving* countries and more to do with the impact of the global economies on the local markets and the market creation dynamics. More specifically, global cities attract waves of unskilled labour forces from these local markets to sustain the night global economies. In the next section I discuss classical Marxist theory employed in the traditional sense of economic anthropology to explain how the role played by capitalism has produced a further class of labour, namely night workers.

Economic Anthropology explanations for capitalism, production and consumption

⁴² Immanuel Maurice Wallerstein, *The Modern World-System* (Academic, 1974). Also, see Ibid.

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ Hania Zlotnik, 'Empirical Identification of International Migration Systems', in *International Migration Systems: A Global Approach*, ed. by Mary M. Kritz, Lin Lean Lim, and Hania Zlotnik (Oxford: Clarendon, 1992), pp. 19-40.

⁴⁵ Ibid.

The tradition of economic anthropology which falls within the scope of political economy has a Marxist inclination.⁴⁶ This tradition of anthropological political economy describes society as divided into two spheres, of production and consumption into cultural analysis (or at best three: production, consumption, and exchange).⁴⁷

At the centre of this school of thought is the concept of 'mode of production' (MoP). This concept is found in Karl Marx's later writings when he analysed capitalism in terms of struggle between the classes, i.e. there are no individuals per se, but classes that exploit one another and therefore are in a continual antagonism.⁴⁸ In short, the owners of the means of production or the 'ruling class' exploit the primary producers who offer their labour power.

One salient feature of capitalism is division. Divisions are made between domestic and economic spheres, producers and exploited, makers and consumers or nurturing societies and slave-owning societies. In other words, owners of means of production are divided from workers, workers are alienated from the production and creation process, peripheric (or societies nurturing highly skilled professionals) divided from core societies (receiving through selection the professionals). More pertinent to this study is the division between owners of business and workers employed by the former or a divide between the upper-middle class and immigrants and the population at the periphery of mainstream society, the latter one keeping the global cities (London, New York) going at night. As with Melbin's findings,⁴⁹ in Sharman and Sharman's⁵⁰ study on nightshifts in New York same trends

⁴⁶ Suman Nath, 'Political Economy in Anthropology', www.blogger.co.uk
<<http://sumananthromaterials.blogspot.co.uk/2011/10/political-economy-in-anthropology.html>> [accessed 13.10.2011]

⁴⁷ David Graeber, *Possibilities : essays on hierarchy, rebellion and desire* (Edinburgh: AK, 2007), p. 87.

⁴⁸ Andrew Heywood, *Political ideologies : an introduction* 4th edn (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2007), p. 122.

⁴⁹ Murray Melbin, *Night as frontier : colonizing the world after dark* (New York and London: Free Press ; Collier Macmillan, 1987).

⁵⁰ Ibid.

emerged. These studies show that more men than women work nightshifts, and immigrants who were over-represented in low-paying, low prestige jobs working nightshifts were foreigners of African American, Asian, Hispanic or Latino descent; whites were the lowest in number. Similar findings suggest also that among Britain's night labourers one in five women between 16-25 do night work regularly, and young people (aged 16-19) are on the increase from 10% to 18% in the last ten years.⁵¹ These figures indicate that in Britain there is a new strata of people that form a different cluster of regular night workers. One repercussion of the increased tuition fees in higher education is argued by this researcher to be behind the rise of the above figures and I add that this may also indicate effects of globalisation providing grounds for a further class of labour, i.e. night labourers. In the next section I employ classicist Marxist theory to explain the point I made above regarding night labourers.

Das Kapitalism

From a Classical Marxist perspective, the capitalist society is engaged in creation of wealth and power through a surplus extracted at the expense of those who lead an existence of survival.⁵² The reference to 'surplus value', as I understand it, is made to explain that for the corporations to make a profit they need to pay their wage-labourers less 'than the value their labour generates.'⁵³

If from a classical Marxist standpoint, capitalism is nothing but a 'form of economic organization where some important actors are using money to make more money'⁵⁴ I suggest that one way to render this perspective is to contrast the capitalist societies with non-capitalist societies.

⁵¹ Ibid, p. 8.

⁵² Ibid, p. 122.

⁵³ Ibid, p. 122.

⁵⁴ Ibid.

Graeber provides such contrast. He explains that the non-capitalist societies focus on the self-realisation of human beings where the object of production is not the end result (e.g. wealth), but the creation of social relations amongst people.⁵⁵ The focus is instead on actions and processes (from poetry to planting onions) by which people shape one another, and as Graeber⁵⁶ explains they are:

- a) always motivated by meanings (ideas)
- b) always proceed through a concrete medium (material)

But capitalism Graeber says,

*'Is not a state of mind but a matter of objective structures, which allow wealth and power to be translated into abstract forms in which they can be endlessly expanded and reproduced.'*⁵⁷

The distinction Graeber makes, I think, lays in the fact that non-capitalist societies are concerned with the individuals and their self-realisation through processes that may bring them together as opposed to capitalist societies' system to produce wealth and concomitantly alienate the workers from their labour. The concern for the latter is to produce commodities, not useful and meaningful products. Therefore, there is no need for corporations to provide creative activities so that workers socialise and engage with their self-development, especially when robots can produce and make more profit for them. However, growth of capital happens through expansion.

The 'capital is a living entity, which constantly seeks to expand – expansion is the key of survival for capitalist firms.'⁵⁸ Here, it is useful to think of the aggressive expansion of food store chains. Since 1978, the working hours in 82% of 6,599 'Seven-11' food stores had been

⁵⁵ Ibid.

⁵⁶ Ibid.

⁵⁷ Ibid. Pp?

⁵⁸ Ibid, p. 103.

extended beyond the 7am – 11pm, operating night daily. In Britain, just before the 1998 Christmas, Tesco supermarket chain surprised its competitors by opening selected stores for nights. There are many more examples that illustrate expansion of night economy.

Marx however, was concerned with the fact that expansion leads to over production, which drives capitalist economies into stagnation with visible economic crises reflected in unemployment and more misery and struggles for the weak working class. It is timely to ponder on the aspects that Marx drew attention, such as the deepening of the economic crises that Western capitalist societies experience at present.

Marx's perspective is also relevant to our discussion because it explains the ways in which migrants coming from societies in transition to capitalism into mature capitalist societies and become workers who are generally preferred by corporations because they accept to be paid less for their work than the nationals of the capitalist countries. Yet, capitalistic societies offer possibilities and opportunities. As participants in this study argue, here in London, a global capitalistic city is where they pursue their goals. I share their views as I have been researching some social phenomena and now I am writing up this study within a capitalist system mode of production, which has afforded me the means (e.g. loans, scholarship, grants) to discover knowledge.

From a production perspective, producing human beings in a particular society is a very high cost/investment, and not very profitable at first as humans are incapable of producing in their first ten-fifteen years of life. Migrant workers who travel from one city/country to another in search for better opportunities are prone to risks and de-skilling when accepting whatever work becomes available in the destination city/country. Examples of contemporary migrant

workers who become de-skilled, come from highly educated East-European doctors and Thai women who move to Canada and become living-in carers.

A consumption-side explanation of the capitalist societies is that consumers spend money on products that were manufactured someplace else without knowledge of the producers. An example of consumers as barely choosers illustrates the point: to 'Buy American' is less meaningful nowadays when parts of Honda are made in the USA and Ford cars leave the assembly lines in Mexico.⁵⁹ He calls this consumption fetishism, when consumers mistake freedom of choosing a product for free choice.

In summary, the 'intellectual agenda'⁶⁰ of this study is to show that capitalism offers possibilities to those who look for them, but I disagree with the capitalist system of producing wealth at the expense of day or night wage-labourers, and with some societies benefiting from highly skilled workers prepared and educated in others, peripheric societies, and with the fact that capitalistic divisions between those who produce and those who consume deepens. However, the consumerist behaviour has exacerbated since the Industrial Revolution with its heavily mechanised processes has allowed for the extension of work around the clock, i.e. night-work to sustain the expansion of night economy. In the next section I look into the empirical studies on the night economy with its positive and negative effects on the night workers.

⁵⁹ Arjun Appadurai, *Modernity at large: cultural dimensions of globalization* (United States: University of Minnesota Press, 1996), p. 42.

⁶⁰ *Ibid*, p. 175.

C. Empirical studies of night economy

Prevalence of night work in Great Britain

This sub-section first survey a range of evidence on night and its adjacent topics. Then, it discusses findings of recent research carried out with London's night workers that illustrate very few positive consequences in comparison to the negative consequences. I highlight also that night workers are almost unseen in the literature. However, there have been studies carried out on the nocturnal life.

Evidence that night is a space for crime and disorder⁶¹ in certain neighbourhoods has long been in the public debate, but less have researchers have contended that due to certain design in urban planning crime levels raise and violence increases during the nights in the cities.⁶²

Ethnographers have found that a certain consumerist culture is linked to social exclusion through differential access to night life.⁶³ Furthermore, Rowe and Bavinton Britain has difficulty to follow transformations from a night-life to night economy, however it does lead the changes in this direction when compared with the continental Europe.⁶⁴

Additionally, researchers have connected night with territoriality after dark⁶⁵, community policing the streets after dark and urged the individuals should take some responsibilities for improving safety in their neighbourhood. Finally, Williams enquired the effect of government policies on people's behaviour at night in public spaces under surveillance, and identified challenges for further research on night spaces and homogenisation; night space

⁶¹ E. Groff and E. S. McCord, 'The role of neighborhood parks as crime generators', *Security Journal*, 25 (2012).

⁶² M. Roberts, 'Planning, urban design and the night-time city: Still at the margins?', *Criminology & Criminal Justice*, 9 (2009).

⁶³ P. Hadfield, 'From threat to promise - Nightclub 'security', governance and consumer elites', *British Journal of Criminology*, 48 (2008), p. 429.

⁶⁴ D. Rowe and N. Bavinton, 'Tender for the night: After-dark cultural complexities in the night-time economy', *Continuum-Journal of Media & Cultural Studies*, 25 (2011).

⁶⁵ R. Samuels, 'After-dark design, night animation, and interpersonal interaction: Toward a community-security paradigm', *Journal of Architectural and Planning Research*, 22 (2005).

and resistance; meanings associated with night, and night practices that lead to marginalisation and exclusion.⁶⁶ Night leisure and fear of night-crime are two most salient features that researchers associated with the night. However, ethnographic research on night work is lacking from the literature and this is where it is hoped that this ethnographic study would fill the gap. Moreover, this research aims to analyse processes of migration in close relation to a social field hardly associated with, such as Europeanisation. Until this point in the discussion will be reached the positive and negative effects of nightshifts on the night workers will be discussed next.

Effects on night workers

a. Negative consequences

Night is a natural phenomenon, but working at night is not. However unnatural night work is to our body and mind rhythm it seems to be increasingly accepted in a globalised, night society.

*'One quality of globalisation is reflected in the expansion and the stretching of social relations, activities, and interdependencies.'*⁶⁷

I chose this definition out of the many that attempt to define *globalisation* (as a process, condition, system, force, and age) because I found it encapsulates two key aspects that reflect the capitalist societies' tendency to expand and stretch into other societies and incorporate them within the world market economy. Furthermore, these two key aspects resemble the stretch of the production to the night cycle and for that reason Will Norman⁶⁸ argues, that modern industry with its expensive technology needs to be operated and manned night so that in the long run it becomes more cost-effective.

⁶⁶ Robert Williams, 'Night Spaces: Darkness, Deterritorialization, and Social Control', *Space and Culture*, 11 (2008), 526-28.

⁶⁷ Manfred B. Steger, *Globalization: a very short introduction* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2003), p. 11.

⁶⁸ *Ibid.*

Adjacent to this need, is the expectation that services should be available throughout the night. As we move towards a night society,⁶⁹ the number of night workers will increase in order to maintain the global cities night economy. These workers' rhythm of life and circadian rhythms become worse when up at night and needing to perform 'tasks that involve manual dexterity or mental arithmetic for example.'⁷⁰ Also, patterns of socialisations change. For example, an informant working at the Victoria Station in London told us how he socialises at 6am, after he finishes his nightshift and goes to the gym. That is where and how he meets people to socialise.

Norman's findings show that night shift workers are exposed to a series of dangers and risks. Among these is the increased likelihood of health problems, both mental and physical. The fact that night workers jeopardise their health is evident to this team of researchers⁷¹ from Canada and Norway who reviewed and provided a meta-analysis of 34 studies and more than two million people investigated. They assessed the risk ratios for vascular morbidity, vascular mortality, or all-cause mortality in relation to shift work. Of relevance to health risks due to night work they found that the risk of stroke was 5% higher in night shift workers than other shift work and intriguingly,

*'...women with morning chronotype preference and exposure to night work ...had even higher risks ... This last finding may suggest a role for disruption of circadian rhythm in the pathogenesis of shift work associated breast cancer.'*⁷²

Many night workers that Norman interviewed have shown also a very poor life style, poor diet, and 'a propensity to smoke and drink more alcohol.'⁷³ They are more likely to have accidents during night-shifts due to fatigue and lack of concentration. In addition, they are

⁶⁹ Leon Kreitzman, *The 24 hour society* (London: Profile, 1999).

⁷⁰ Ibid, p. 86.

⁷¹ V. Manav Vyas and others, 'Shift Work and Vascular Events: Systematic Review and Meta-analysis', *British Medical Journal*, 345 (2012).

⁷² Ibid, p. 4.

⁷³ Ibid.

prone to have more car accidents on the way to and from work due to tiredness. Furthermore, vulnerability and poor or lack of social life are two of the factors that put pressure on those night workers who are in relationships or have children.

Britain's night workforce is reaching almost 1.4 million night workers.⁷⁴ The people who run the hospitals and ambulance services at night, help us to cancel lost or stolen credit cards, Samaritans, sewers, sleep researchers, street cleaners are unseen and unsupported, says Norman, when compared to those who do equivalent work during the day. More worryingly they are unaware of the negative effects this type of shift has on their psychological and physical wellbeing, as well as on their safety when carried out regularly for a long period.

The night migrant labourers are particularly vulnerable because, as one participant told me, it is more dangerous of being attacked or not being paid the fare whilst on night-duty as a night taxi driver. Biological clocks found in plants, animals and humans have an essential purpose – to regulate the body and mind, ‘and to allow the organisms to maintain an internal temporal order and to anticipate change.’⁷⁵ Till we find a way to adjust safely our biological clocks, I suspect, night workers like the ones Norman spoke will complain by extreme fatigue and mental strains. Besides, it impacts on communities, on the way culture is transferred from one place to another and on the social lives of those working nightshifts. There are many disadvantages, but for now I turn to positive consequences.

b. Positive consequences

As this and other studies show advantages are outweighed by disadvantages. Norman goes further and says that night workers face many dangers. There are though positive consequences as well. For example, there are economic arguments that I raised at the

⁷⁴ Ibid.

⁷⁵ Ibid, p. 88.

beginning of the section, i.e. the technology becomes more cost-effective if manned night. Beyond that, 'entrepreneurs ... are attracted to the promise of fortunes in the night.'⁷⁶ For economic gains, with the arrival of Industrial Revolution businesses have squeezed lands of what they could produce at night from it, exploited the night hours and 'recruited large numbers of night workers ... to multiply the number of goods produced in factories.'⁷⁷

From the perspective of night workers nightshifts provides them with some advantages. They can spend more time with family; others say that they call their friends more often; remuneration is better for some and they appreciate there is less traffic at night.

Academic accounts which associate the incessant night economy and night work are very few and this is a negative aspect. They range from those emphasising crime against security at night, to those focused on differential access to the night life, and those focused on the role of city planning in increasing safety at night. Where I aim to fill a gap with this study is in the area where night work is rarely if at all associated with the consequences lived by Romanian migrants in an age of Europeanisation. In the next chapter, I explain how I carried out this study, the strategy and methods I used to collect the data.

⁷⁶ Ibid, p. 15.

⁷⁷ Ibid, p. 15.

Methodology: Data and Methods

'Tell us the story of your life' - Anon

Introduction

Doing ethnographic fieldwork entails that the qualitative researcher focuses on the 'object – the *thing itself* as the European says – and its meaning, with no sense of the historical peculiarity of this effect we call the *thing itself*.'⁷⁸ Mitchell's idea is useful in grasping the position of a participant observer who observes her/his objects of research, as if the world was set up as an exhibition regardless of its history. In the process of arranging her/his subjects of study s/he comes with some conceived ideas about the world about to be researched.

The 'world', in my study, is the socio-economic context by which Romanians have migrated to work as part of London's night economy on the backdrop of the Europeanisation process. I alternate roles between participant/non-participant observer and interviewer. I shift my position between these roles depending on when, where and with whom I am involved, observe or interview. Also, as a researcher I adopt a semi-detached position trying to grasp what is going on from the inside (accompanying the day or night shift workers). So, I am involved and struggling to understand the interactions between the social actors from a critical point of view, while I try and remain visible to the people involved. In this section I recount why I did my fieldwork. But first, I briefly describe why I chose this subject?

After readings of theoretical and empirical research on the night economy and nocturnal work it became visible to me that migrant night workers in GB, in particular from the new member states of the EU were invisible from the scholarly literature. To this date there is not one

⁷⁸ T. Mitchell, 'The World as Exhibition', *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 31 (1989), 232.

empirical study conducted on Eastern European migrants working nights in Britain. However, since a global city like London requires that people working around the night clock I decided to include in the study also the traditional nine-to-five working or day workers in order to get an understanding of what it means to be a working migrant during one day in the city.

Why do fieldwork? I did fieldwork because I wanted to gather information until now absent on Romanian migrant workers working day and night shifts as part of London's night economy and on their migrant trajectories since Romania entered the EU. I chose anthropological theory and methodology for this fieldwork for several reasons. Firstly, I conducted previously participant observation with beggars and buskers on the London streets during the day. Secondly, the novel approach to ethnographic research is illustrated in Sandhu's⁷⁹ immersions into the urban night, which I followed to conduct night research. Thirdly, because the ethnographic method allowed me to get involved with the migrants, doing day and night observations and study their words and actions, and analyse if what they say what they do converges with what I observe in the field. Lastly, the essence of the qualitative approach is to examine a set of events through the perspective of people who are being studied.⁸⁰ The emphasis, in qualitative research is on understanding the participants' social context and the processes contributing to a particular circumstance, i.e. how things change.⁸¹

However, the researchers' choice of strategy (methodology) and tactics (methods) are influenced by her/his epistemological and ontological positions, theoretical assumptions and

⁷⁹ Sukhdev Sandhu and Artangel, *Night haunts : a journey through the London night* (London: Verso, 2010).

⁸⁰ Gary King, Robert O. Keohane, and Sidney Verba, *Designing social inquiry : scientific inference in qualitative research* (Princeton, N.J. ; Chichester: Princeton University Press, 1994), p. 531.

⁸¹ Gary D. Bouma, G. B. J. Atkinson, and Beverly R. Dixon, *Handbook of social science research* Dixon, *A handbook of social science research* 2nd ed. / Gary D. Bouma, G. B. J. Atkinson. edn (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1995).

the ethical implications in doing an ethnographic study. In the next sub-section, I will discuss very briefly first the two concepts (*ontology* and *epistemology*) that influenced my strategy as well as the theoretical assumptions underpinning my tactics. Then, I will explain how I collected and analysed the data.

Ontology and Epistemology

Ontology (what is) and epistemology (what it means to know) are two key concepts that social scientists should consider because they impact on the direction of their research. Marsh and Furlong compare ontology and epistemology with the 'researcher's skin and cannot be put on and taken off like a sweater, whenever it is suitable.'⁸² In other words, a particular starting point of research will lead to a particular strategy as well as precise theoretical language.

Crotty's 'scaffolding learning'⁸³ model refers to *ontology*, epistemology, methodology, methods and sources as the key components of social research. Crotty's model is distinct from Grix's model of 'building blocks'⁸⁴ in that he insists on the initial structures of research leaving to 'the learner to establish long term structures.'⁸⁵ He explains that 'ontological and epistemological issues merge together'⁸⁶ and simplifies the initial structure for research. His approach is that researchers should not engage in ontological explanations unless they are discussing the very essence of being. Otherwise, ontology and epistemology concepts should be merged.

In Blaikies' view, ontological claims are 'assumptions about one's *view* on the nature of social reality - what it looks like, what units make it up.'⁸⁷ In other words, if I believe that the world I am about to investigate is independent, 'out there' and separate from the social actors

⁸² David Marsh and Paul Furlong, 'A Skin, not a Sweater: *Ontology and Epistemology in Political Science*', in *Theory and Methods in Politics Science*, ed. by David Marsh and Gerry Stoker (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2002), pp. 17-41 (p. 17).

⁸³ Michael Crotty, *The Foundations of Social Research: Meaning and Perspective in the Research Process* (London: Sage, 1998), p. 1.

⁸⁴ Ibid, p. 175.

⁸⁵ Ibid, p. 1.

⁸⁶ Ibid, p. 10.

⁸⁷ Norman Blaikie, *Approaches to Social Inquiry* (Cambridge: Polity, 2000), p. 8.

involved, then I am assumed to come from an ontological *objectivist* tradition or *foundationalist* approach and I hold a positivist perspective on the world.⁸⁸ In contrast, if I assume that the world is socially constructed by the actors and the meanings derived are the result of the social actors' interactions, then I have adopted the ontological *constructionist* tradition or *anti-foundationalist* approach.⁸⁹ I have adopted an anti-foundationalist position and believe that the world is socially constructed.

Epistemology,

'... Is concerned with providing a philosophical grounding for deciding what kinds of knowledge are possible and how we can ensure that they are both adequate and legitimate.'⁹⁰

Marsh and Smith argue that *epistemology* has a crucial position in research as it shapes 'what ones studies, how one studies it and what conclusions one draws from research.'⁹¹ Gray⁹² argues that although, researchers cannot capture the 'whole truth', they can offer a 'version of the truth.' In other words, social contexts may be interpreted from different angles and researchers, depending on their life experience and ethnographic position, focus on different aspects of their practice to produce meanings.

My epistemological position is based on Crotty's 'scaffolding' and has several implications for my research. First, I share the participants' language and have shared for many years the same culture. Prior to my fieldwork, I had knowledge of Romania's past and present and its current economic-socio-politic situation. Therefore, I did not enter the field as a complete stranger.⁹³ Secondly, and more importantly, by understanding and interpreting the social

⁸⁸ Alan Bryman, *Social Research Methods* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2001), p. 264.

⁸⁹ Ibid.

⁹⁰ Mary Maynard, *Methods, practice and epistemology: The debate about feminism and research* (London: Taylor & Francis, 1994), p. 10.

⁹¹ David Marsh and Martin J. Smith, 'There is More Than One Way to do Political Science: On Different Ways to Study Policy Networks', *Political Studies*, 49 (2001).

⁹² Ann Gray, *Research practice for cultural studies : ethnographic methods and lived cultures* Reprint. edn (London: Sage, 2004), p. 21.

⁹³ Martyn Hammersley and Paul Atkinson, *Ethnography : principles in practice* 2nd edn (London: Routledge, 1995).

world constructed by my participants, I aim to capture the participants' lived experiences whilst at the same time I see myself being part of the social world constructing it through my own interpretations of it.

Data

The study aimed at capturing the every day and night lived experiences of Romanian migrants working as part of London's night economy, considering that migrancy involves adopting a 'temporary identity'⁹⁴, and adapting to new environments for the purpose of travelling to earn money and live abroad. I have decided to focus on London, a 'global city', as it was the site that offered the maximum of job opportunities for migrants working as part of its night economy. The sample was composed through a mixed of random criteria with the view to include participants from various walks of life and to ensure a certain degree of representativeness. The evidence highlights the processes behind the choice of migrants' destination for travel, the reasons why some have ended up doing unskilled jobs, and the sacrifices others make to prevail in highly competitive jobs.

I have started collecting the data very early in my research, in particular because I planned to do observations and informal conversations, for instance when I accompanied nightshift workers. These were followed by detailed field note-taking, immediately after the fieldwork. Where observations were not possible I complemented with interview and in-depth conversations, which I carried out during the day. I collected the data over a period of three months, duration in which I did night observations, had informal conversations and semi-structured interviews during night and day, either on the sites participants worked at, in public locations (e.g. cafés, train stations) or officials' own offices.

⁹⁴ Ibid, p. 10.

The data from this study comes from several informal conversations with one night worker and three interviews with other night workers. I conducted conversations with four men. Only one man was married; three had their extended families in Romania and two were living together with their wives in London. None had children. Out of the four Romanians, one was of mixed Romanian and Roma ethnic group, and the age range was between late 20's to late 30's. In addition, I interviewed two Romanian officials based in London and one British MP.

All Romanian migrants were working as part of London's night job market at the time of my fieldwork. Two men were working in relatively qualified and stressful jobs (night trader and auditor) and two were working in low skilled jobs (night taxi driver and barman). All were legally working - three were employed and one was registered as self-employed taxi driver.

Initially, I aimed at completing the sample of my study by relying on the 'snowball technique', considered as the most realistic for 'hidden populations'.⁹⁵ The problem I was faced with during the early stage of my research was that except on two occasions, no new participant was referred to me by somebody I interviewed previously or any acquaintance. However, I addressed this problem in the following phase. I have received positive responses from announcements I placed on-line (e.g. websites and social media, such as Facebook), two recommendations from acquaintances as well by approaching directly migrant workers whilst I was doing fieldwork. In each case, I would refer the potential interviewees to the project profile I have set up on-line for this purpose. Thus, where possible, I wanted them to become familiar with the topic prior to any arrangement.

⁹⁵ Elizabeth Y. Lambert and Abuse National Institute on Drug Abuse National Institute on Drug, *The collection and interpretation of data from hidden populations* (Rockville MD: National Institute on Drug Abuse, 1990).

As a flip side to the day conversations, night research was very different. The locations were the people worker often were in closed environments, and the duration of a night fieldwork could last between 4-9 hours, sometimes starting as early as 9pm and finishing at 5-6am. Other times, the nocturnal research would start at 11pm and finish at 3-4am.

The atmosphere – ‘what was going on’ – could differ from very quiet to busy, but the majority of situations were impromptu. When participants allowed me to observe their work place, they were eager to talk about their lives, sometimes to quite an intimate level, than during day research. For example, one participant allowed me to be on site during one night shift. Whilst I was there, his night duty manager seized the opportunity to talk to me, which was very unexpected and unplanned. Examples such as this one reflect that spontaneity during night fieldwork played a part in tapping into different strata than those captured by research which used gatekeepers to get access. Also, it may have enriched the representativeness of my research sample.

By departing from the traditional ethnographic methodology and complementing this with night research it meant that I had to address certain requirements. I regarded these night workers as a vulnerable population.

On one hand, their vulnerability was reflected in the fact that whilst under the work restrictions on GB job market against Romanians, some of the participants' employment status in GB was uncertain and made them feel unsafe towards any contact coming outside their peers;

For those reasons, I had to ensure that the interviewees' safety is not put at risk by contacting them through intermediaries or gatekeepers i.e. support project groups, Police and jeopardise my research. This, I have managed successfully, by contacting them directly, preserving their anonymity throughout and adhering to an ethical practice informed by a subject-centred approach, which has been approved by the UCL Ethics committee prior to commencing the research. Their names have been changed for that purpose.

On the other hand, besides the usual risks night workers take, i.e. health and safety risks, accidents at work and on the way home from a night shift, some of the Romanian night labourers I interviewed were subject to the same work restrictions regulations as I mentioned above, and that added to their vulnerability. Whilst legally employed (as they assured me), they were entitled by law only to a certain amount of weekly working hours. For example, the students are allowed to work in GB a maximum of 20 hours per week. This also meant that some participants like the barman (see results section) felt vulnerable and was evasive when it came to explaining his employment status. Hence, I see migrant night labourers not just vulnerable, but also a 'hidden population'.

I have taken field and interview notes, which I complemented with self-reflexive observations of the ethnographic fieldwork. I transcribed these notes and observations, and throughout the research I kept them under an encrypted password known only to myself. Data was analysed in accordance with the themes and sub-themes embedded in the original research and sub-research questions.

Methods

I have chosen the biographical method of life story to collect and analyse portions of the participants' lives. The choice of method for this study is a pragmatic one. Namely, I am interested to find out concrete information about the participants' migration trajectories, and the networks they used to migrate and find work in London's night economy. I am interested not in how people became to be who they are at the time of the interview, but in their life events that led them to taking a 'temporary identity',⁹⁶ and the narratives they construct in rapport to the social contexts, e.g. Romania's accession to the EU, pre-migration lives and working climate in GB.

The semi-structured interviews and the informal conversations were in-depth and unstructured. Therefore, the choice of method was dictated by and aimed at capturing migrants' accounts of their lives inclusive of both concrete, factual information as well as 'sections of life stories that contain enough number of narratives and their relations to permit us to study the creation of coherence for similarly problematic chains of events'⁹⁷ and compare how different speakers construct similar types of narratives.

Life story as a method is 'thoroughly subjective, in the sense that it is the expression of a particular subjectivity.'⁹⁸ Bertaux argues that too many scholars have criticised this quality, subjectivity of the subjects' skills in talking about her/him.⁹⁹ In other words, the fact that life stories have a degree of sensitivity that does not mean they cannot produce objective

⁹⁶ Ibid.

⁹⁷ C. Linde, *Life stories : the creation of coherence* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1993), p. 52.

⁹⁸ Robin Humphrey, Robert L. Miller, and E. A. Zdravomyslova, *Biographical research in Eastern Europe : altered lives and broken biographies* (Aldershot: Ashgate, 2003), p. 41.

⁹⁹ Ibid.

information. Quite the opposite, life stories (and autobiographies) can be factual. Here is an example, taken from one participant's biography:

Fact: *'I am 33, and have two children, ...'*

More importantly, life stories are primarily interested in the social context, the background information that provides enough material for the researcher to analyse '*what has been done to those people and how they reacted to it*'.¹⁰⁰ Continuing with the above quite:

'... They [the children] are looked after my mother in Romania whilst I work here in GB, to make a future for them.'

I will return to discuss this in greater detail in the results section. For now, I briefly describe the coding system. By taking the realist approach, of generating concepts (organised in themes and sub-themes) from the empirical observations carried out in the field towards abstract concepts.¹⁰¹ This process of evaluation aims at developing concepts based on concrete data ...¹⁰² The concrete stages are: 1) Broad scanning and coding of the material; 2) Re-sorting the material in preliminary categories; 3) Refining the categorisation; and 4) Form new category groupings from extra material.

¹⁰⁰ Ibid, p. 40.

¹⁰¹ Robert L. Miller, *Researching life stories and family histories* (London: SAGE, 2000), p. 114.

¹⁰²

Results

'You won't find your thesis in the next book you read,
You'll find it in your interview transcripts and your field note books'¹⁰³

A long time ago, the City of London was known for its 'long lunches and leisurely working hours.'¹⁰⁴ Nowadays, the City of London or New York City represent extreme cases¹⁰⁵ of global cities with high concentration of highly skilled traders and executives that attract low skilled work force in order to maintain London's night economy.

The night workforce is made of people stocking up shelves in supermarkets, dealing with credit card cancellations, running the emergency services (ambulance, police and firemen) or auditing the work completed by staff that finished the day shift before 18:00. Bankers or traders however, work very long hours to meet tight deadlines, which may cross this boundary before/after 18:00. Radio or TV broadcasters work long hours and night shifts too. But, these highly paid executives and professionals buy solutions to balance work with family life. In contrast, there are the lowly or hourly paid wage-labourers whose working hours stretch from 07am to 11pm who find it extremely difficult to balance work and family life because they work long hours for extra earnings.¹⁰⁶ One top executive explained,

*'When you are in a senior executive position it is much easier to balance work and family ... It is hourly paid staff who have it much harder, particularly when both parents are working. Their time is very constrained.'*¹⁰⁷

The night workers that I had spoken to before their nightshift and/or observed them while they were on night duty represent a mix between low wage skilled workers (taxi driver, barman) and better paid skilled ones in the service sectors (trading and hotelier). See Appendix 1 for a short biography on each participant, which describes some of their family, work backgrounds, pre-migration jobs, and motivations for leaving from Romania. All their names have been changed to preserve their anonymity.

¹⁰³ Ibid, p. 175.

¹⁰⁴ Ibid, p. 26.

¹⁰⁵ Ibid.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid, p. 21.

¹⁰⁷ Ibid, p. 27.

Their shift pattern varies, and likewise their duties. For example, Mihai, the night city trader and Rică, the auditor have similar shift patterns. The former works five nights out of seven from 22:00-06:00, the latter from 23:00-07:00, but he is restricted to work maximum of 20 hours a week; they both work full-time and this, according to the Labour Force Survey classes this category as permanent night work, usually between 18:00-06:00.¹⁰⁸ The same statistics show that in Britain there are 321,830 permanent workers.

Leon the barman and Cătălin the taxi driver work on different patterns mainly because the taxi driver is self-employed and does not stay on night duty after midnight unless there are customers. Leon works on regular nightshifts that finish in the early hours of the morning, between 02:00-03:00. Although, there is no clear-cut category to assign, their shifts continue past midnight, it is 5-7 days per week; this defines these people as permanent night workers.¹⁰⁹

Out of the four participants only the barman found his night job through networking. Whilst it is common, as Mai¹¹⁰ previously found, that friends and family provide the economic support to newly arrived working migrants, this is not Leon's case. He was self-sufficient during his first three months in GB when he was searching for a job. He began looking for work in November 2011 and in January 2012 he started to work at a night café bar in London; a job he eventually found through another Romanian who was sharing the accommodation with him, in East London.

Neither of the participants worked nights before coming to GB nor were they planning to do it on a long-term basis. They explained why they were working nightshifts varied. Mihai used *conjectural* - for him it was a short-medium term necessity in order to learn the Asian trading market; Rică was constrained by legislation, but also saw it as a sacrifice in order to develop a career during day time, and for Cătălin it was better *remuneration* – saving money faster so he could go back to Romania. Leon knew also that this job was only a temporary post till he joined a Think-Tank organisation on a day job. All four participants saw nightshift as being done in conjunction with other plans or purpose, and only for a while.

¹⁰⁸ Ibid, p. 7.

¹⁰⁹ Ibid, p. 7.

¹¹⁰ Ibid.

In a combined effort similar to Teresa Gowan's approach, the participants' words, the field notes, and my observations aim to portray the voices, descriptions and evidence¹¹¹ coming through the unfolding lives of these night workers, in a way that Howard S. Becker calls it 'telling about society.'¹¹²

13 years ago, Leon Kreitzman argued that we are moving towards a night society.¹¹³ The participants' accounts show that this society has been already transformed in that direction. The next three themes will demonstrate it and look into how these participants negotiate a balance between night work and family, their aspirations and plans for the future, and how night work impacts on them.

A. Socio-economic background and reasons to migrate

Notes from the fieldwork diary:

Cristian was a truck driver and policeman in Romania. Since he moved to GB with his family he does flower arrangements and deliveries at night. One of his customers is based at the hotel where one of the participants in this study works as night auditor and receptionist. The first night when they met Rică, 28, was at the reception desk. They are both from Romania and anytime Rică is on nightshift they talk about their everyday concerns. During one conversation I had with Rică he told me that Cristian was unhappy living in Romania. In Cristian's words, 'all you can do there [Romania] nowadays is to exist from day to day without improving or progressing'.

Similarly, Cătălin, a 29 year old night taxi driver in a dangerous area of North London gives me a specific example of the current day-to-day living in Romania now:

At present it's hard in Romania. An average salary is 780RON [£138.00]. 500RON [£88.67] costs just the gas, heating, water. How can you live in Romania with this money? And how can you save and make some future there?

¹¹¹ Teresa Gowan and Inc ebrary, *Hobos, hustlers, and backsliders : homeless in San Francisco* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2010).

¹¹² Howard Saul Becker, *Telling about society* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2007).

¹¹³ Ibid.

Nonetheless, not all participants in this study share the same views and pre-migration experiences and each of the participants had different motivations why they migrated to London. Leon says that *'I want to continue my education at Cambridge, with a Masters course'*. He was not financially motivated. In fact, he had saved £3,000 while he worked as a Project Manager in Romania and for the first three months when he was searching for a job in London he was self-sufficient leaving from the savings. An opposite reaction comes from Mihai who says that

Obviously Romanians come to London because of financial gains. ... I left Romania because I studied finance there and the place to be for those who did finance is London. That's the reason why I came to London. I had the chance to travel elsewhere, but London is the place I liked and wanted to work.

Leon told me he *'was fresh off the boat'*, meaning he just arrived few months ago. He had been in GB before. In 2009 he visited London with his brother and then girlfriend. He already decided then that he will return, to study, live in this culture and pursue his higher goals in this country. He had been in GB for just a few months and since the beginning of January 2012 he started to work as barman in one of London's famous café bars on evening shifts lasting till 02:00-03:00 am.

Leon's migration trajectory appears straight forward in comparison to Rică's. Rică is an ambitious young man. He finished his BA in Economics in Romania and then went to the US where he studied at a Bible College while he did an internship in the Hotelier Industry. Then, he worked illegally for a year. This happened in 2007 – 2009. His mother sponsored his trip to the US with \$2,000. He returned her the money from the \$4,000 he had saved while he was in the US, and in 2010 he came to GB. This is what he did after paying the debts to his mother.

On his return from the US, he paid an agency in Cluj, Romania to find him a course in GB. The agency found him an English language course in Brighton where he studied for two months. He paid in advance the college fees of £800 (this price included £300 fees including

work placement). He arrived in GB in 2010 to study English. Within two months of the course the college closed down. He was not refunded and needed to search for work and accommodation while he lived on the savings he had prior to arriving to GB. Although, that impacted on his plans he knew before he left Romania that he was prone to face some risks.

Unlike in Agustín's scenario where sex workers 'earn €5,000 a month and repay their debts quickly'¹¹⁴, night workers like Rică have to work for several months or maybe a year in order to repay their debt bondage. Moreover, the bondage becomes a drawback when, for example, he needs to borrow more money from work colleagues to go and visit his family in Romania. The bondage eventually becomes an obstacle if it perpetuates. As reflected in his migration trajectory, it may be the case. This however, illustrates that migrancy stimulated through creation of false possibilities (often unfulfilled) complicate the day-to-day lives of migrants and makes them financially vulnerable.

In summary, the main findings of this section illustrate that the state of decay in countries like Romania that are in transition to capitalism determines, pushes people (in this study the educated and skilled young professionals) to find alternative ways to fulfil possibilities.

B. Being a Romanian working migrant living in London

The working climate in Great Britain

It is worth mentioning first that although the information Rică gave me during one of our conversations matches the field notes taken after a night's observation carried out separately these accounts reveals a different demeanour in Rică's behaviour. The words I quote below belong to Rică. When I met him that day he was relaxed and comfortable. The observation was taken while Rică was on his night shift with his manager around and my supervisor with

¹¹⁴ Ibid, p. 71.

whom I did the fieldwork that night. The field notes¹¹⁵ show that Rică was a less talkative and quite shy when I met him during the night shift with his manager around. Being on a vocational placement meant he could work like any student, 20 hours a week.

The conversation with Rică was a bit disappointing, he seemed uncomfortable to talk. We asked him about the scheme under which he was working there: he was actually there on a kind of internship, or work (vocational) placement. We got the impression that it was a bit dubious, i.e. the legality of his position. He was hesitant to talk about his status, which may have been rather uncomfortable questions for him to answer. He has indeed finished a BA in Romania, but now he is doing a vocational course (BTEC Extended Diploma¹¹⁶), and he does not need to go to school for that really, only two weeks a year or so, quite a strange construction.

I saw Rică three weeks later, in the same Moroccan tea house we first met. During the discussion I asked him to explain how the legislation in this country affects him. He responded,

At the moment I work on the basis of the yellow card. [I interjected: What are the restrictions for the yellow card?] Normally, these are for students, only part-time, Romanians can work 20 hours per week. The other option is the vocational skill course, and this allows you to work whilst studying in the same field (especially in catering, hotelier industries). All Romanians who work legally for one year can apply consequently for a blue card, without work restrictions, more freedom and choice for types of jobs.

I asked Rică, if being restricted to work maximum 20 hours per week is affecting his day-to-day situation and what sort of constraints he faced. He replied,

In the current climate, and with the crisis in Romania, and in Europe, indeed there is some selection going on, because if there would be freedom to all foreigners there would be many who would come for a job. But there are problems here in GB with finding work. The current situation does make it more difficult for me for the fact that Romanians have a special case. There is some selection going on. Practically speaking, I have come to GB with different plans, but I was constrained to work nightshifts due to the laws in the country.

So, I asked him if he thinks that the current government stops or prevents immigrants to work in GB. He confessed that,

¹¹⁵ The field note is an extract from the detailed notes taken following the fieldwork carried out as part of this study and the *Nightlaboratory* project under the supervision of Ger Duijzings. I am very grateful for his guidance and support during the night observations we carried out together.

¹¹⁶ The BTEC Level 3 Extended Diploma is a vocational qualification taken in England and Wales and Northern Ireland by people aged 16 and over. The qualification is organised and awarded by the Edexcel Foundation within the BTEC brand. BTEC ND is the highest level of the BTEC structure and is equal to three A-Levels. Source:

http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/BTEC_Extended_Diploma

It's very hard to say. I am not interested in the politics. I don't know what sort of measures the government would take. I believe that the measures they take are meant to stop the influx of immigrants to work in GB, which could flood the market, in a very short time

Cătălin has an opposing reaction to Rică's view on why there are work restrictions against Romanians. He thinks that this is not due to the current political tactics or the economic climate, but a consequence of the negative image that Romanians have created in GB by themselves.

Romanians have given themselves a bad name. They caused this. They rubbed people, they still do; they rub cash machines. He feels strongly that 'when people from the EU come and see the list of bad things Romanians did, how they can give them working rights?'

Cătălin concludes,

I think there are two reasons why Romanians are badly viewed in GB: 1. they just have a bad reputation; 2. Romanians are known as frauds - they rub the system of benefits and that's why they don't get the papers and NINO (GB National Insurance Number)

Whilst Cătălin's words may be true, the difficulties faced by Romanian citizens, may be ripple effects from a combination of factors, such as government tactics in decreasing the inflow of immigrants (from EU and non-EU countries), the current economic climate or the delays caused by UK Border Agency in processing applications of Romanian students.

Rică's next argument, supported by Keith Vaz's, MP statement that entry in the EU without full membership has disadvantaged Romanians is as reliant as Mihai's view that Romanians are included in GB, despite the difficult economic climate facing GB right now. In an earlier section it was explained that the fifth enlargement of the EU, in 2004 included eight European states¹¹⁷ followed by Romania and Bulgaria in 2007. Rică criticizes the fact that Romania was not invited to join the EU together with the other eight European states Romanian citizens are disadvantaged now from getting the same access to the GB job market as the other Eastern European migrants.

Romanians are disadvantaged in comparison to other East Europeans. In a way, as the saying goes, first come, first serve. We arrived a bit later at the table, we get what's left.

In contrast to Rică's view, who arrived post 2007 I bring into discussion Mihai's position, as a Romanian-British migrant who has arrived in GB almost twelve years ago.

¹¹⁷ This expansion wave of EU into Central and Eastern Europe included Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, Slovenia, Slovakia, the Czech Republic, Estonia and Hungary.

The normality of day-to-day life in Great Britain

Notes from the fieldwork

At a fashion event organised by the Romanian Institute of Culture I made an acquaintance who said that she knows her Romanian neighbour that works nights. She asked him and a few weeks after our conversation at this event I receive an email from Mihai, a Romanian in his thirties who works as a night city trader in London. We met on Sunday, March 4th 2012, around 21:00, one hour before he was about to start his first night shift for that week. It was 21:15 when I suggested to him that maybe we should find a quiet place to sit down and do the interview. We walked towards Starbucks in Liverpool Street where he bought his coffee before we met. It has closed by then. So, we sat in an eatery.

My first question was about the earlier days when he left Romania twelve years ago to come to GB. He remembered that at the time some family members were encouraging him to leave Romania, but others were against it. However, I felt that he was evasive when it came to this topic [his pre-migration experience] and gave me very little information. I decided to change the tactic and ask him something related to his present experience. As a night trader in the City of London, do you think Romanians are included or excluded in the socio-political structures in the EU? At which he answered:

Here? [He paused as if giving consideration to the question] comparing with the rest of Europe, I think that in GB it's the best out of all countries in Europe. In the sense that they [Romanians] are most included. [Can you think of an example?] No, but I go back to what I said initially. These [British] are the most liberal [in Europe]. When you think in general terms, you find some crazy MP from the nationalist party, but generally speaking they are more open compared to Europe. Maybe, maybe, somehow I find it normal that in a period of [economic] crisis; in this crisis it's a bit shit. Indeed, it lasts long, and it's shit because it cannot be seen clearly when it will be over. There are many unknown factors. I think, these circumstances make everyone to show a more nationalistic tendency, but that doesn't mean they [British] are behaving differently towards Romanians. If you were watching TV a few months ago you would have seen a program called 'British jobs for our youth' – this title give some nuance [he laughs] ... You know, it never got to that kind of extreme nationalism, like racism. It's normal, and I think once the crisis is over the people will get back to normal. It's not a tragedy. I imagine that in the rest of Europe is worse

The first thing that strikes me in this vignette is that the notion of 'normality' takes three different nuances: 1. it is normal to have difficulties in a difficult time; 2. in difficult times it is normal to show a nationalistic tendency; and 3. people will 'get back to normal'. Yet, through exploring these dimensions of what is *normal now* (1 & 2) and *will be normal* (3) it seems to me that getting back to normal means to go through a non-normal phase and having

difficulties. This may indicate that in over 12 years since he arrived in Britain Mihai's notion of normality has evolved with his everyday life in GB or that with the passing of time the question over what is normal and what not became more difficult to answer. This latter reflection I made, referring to Mihai's identity positioning implies 'perceived sameness which at the same time implies differences from others.'¹¹⁸ I am not quite sure if in the following example he brought up in our conversation he is questioning his own identity of a Romanian-British (I assume he is naturalised British citizen), but I invite the reader to ponder on,

Another thing, you are a foreigner, settled here for 8-10 years. Are you 100% foreigner? Let's say you have a 40 year old who lived here for 25 years. Is that person a foreigner? If you were to ask that person "where is your home?" They would say, "Where my soul is". I feel Romanian, [says Mihai] but also that I take something from living here; and why not be something of both?! Your life experience is more enriching

Perhaps, it is time to return to the earlier point I made by Rică and Mihai on the situation of Romanian migrants in GB. Rică said that Romanians are disadvantaged while Mihai contradicted it. What binds together these opposing perspectives is that they are reflections on the nature of identity. Duijzings' concept on fluid identities explains that,

*'From a sociological perspective, identity represents primarily a link between the individual and a specific category or group of people. It is based on perceived sameness which at the same time implies differences from others: identity is therefore about classification and the process of associating or equating oneself (or others) with someone or something else.'*¹¹⁹

In other words, Rică identifies himself with a group of Romanians who arrived after 2007 and this group is disadvantaged in his view. By contrast, Mihai is different from Rică because he arrived in GB long before Romania's accession to EU, and associates himself with that group of Romanians, which in his view are included in the British society. Possibly, living in London for a longer period has made Mihai think that *'London is ultimately more accepting of foreigners than in other parts of Europe.'* This statement agrees with Cătălin's, who said:

I don't like London, but I think it's the place where discrimination is very subtle. Unlike in Germany or Italy and Spain where people not just give you harsh looks, but also tell you racist stuff.

¹¹⁸ Gerlachus Duijzings, *Religion and the politics of identity in Kosovo* (London: Hurst & Company, 2000), pp. 3-4.

¹¹⁹ Richard Jenkins, *Social identity* (London ; New York: Routledge, 1996).

C. Focusing on night work in London

In Cătălin's words, *'working people who do night shifts are like 'second world'*.

His statement shocked me. Yet, I did not understand this 'second world' category of people and I asked him what he meant by it. He explains that

Normal people work 7am-7pm; the second world people work night shifts. During the night shifts, he says, the night transforms you. You look different after a while and your mental is affected too. Your thoughts change. It's weird!

However, Cătălin's concept of *'normal people'* working nowadays 7am-7pm would have appeared very different once upon a time, when the City of London was known for its 'long lunches and leisurely working hours.'¹²⁰

Such past times seem long forgotten in the face of the global technology development and the night incessant rhythm of working round-the-clock. The 'city traders, executives and other client-facing staff in the City of London'¹²¹ commit their bodies and minds to this rhythm. Since the 80's city traders, entrusted with billions of pounds by their customers, worked round-the-clock to meet the demands of an already existing night market.

Night services: an open window

I was keen to find out what participants think of London's night economy. As if in a monologue manner Rică asks,

What exactly is the night-economy? Then answers: I think of non-stop services, hotelier industry, touristic services, and medical services. [Rică:] Are these services needed? Yes, there are services that are needed, and there is also a need for the night workforce.

In a similar vein to Rică, Mihai, the city trader illustrates with an example from his area of work why night work is *'absolutely'* vital to London's night economy.

London is a financial hub. The markets are open 24/7. You can't stop! Otherwise, you don't function. Let's think of banks and stock exchanges. They are always open, from Sunday night to Friday night they are open. They have no choice. They have customers from all over the world and every institution of this kind can't interrupt their [night] activity. So, this is positive for the fact that markets are open

¹²⁰ Ibid, p. 26.

¹²¹ Ibid, p. 26.

24/7. Otherwise, not only that they would drop, but they would cease trading altogether. Practically, it is unconceivable without continuous activity in this area.

May it be as Rică and Mihai argue, but Cătălin is not convinced that London's night economy is relying on Romanian working migrants. Yet, he is one of the Romanian migrants who at first, worked from 6pm-6am, every night as a taxi driver.

He describes how he did his job in those days, and how 12h night shifts impacted on his mental and physical wellbeing:

Usually, the customers ring the office and give their cab orders. The drivers pick up these jobs if they agree to do it. If a minicab driver is not on a job from the minicab office if caught by police they risk an offence charge for not declaring taxes. Cătălin says that 'I don't want to make this kind of customers. I don't want to risk my licence for the sake of £25-£30. The only exception I make is for my family.' He stops, looks at me and then rhetorically asks: 'you don't charge family, do you?! They only pay the petrol.

His reflection on the night work reveals inevitable dangers of being assaulted by customers and not being paid. But he learnt, of course, how to deal and cope with it. At the time when we had this conversation he had been a taxi driver for nine months. Three out of nine, he was doing 12h shifts, back to back, every night. Besides that, the greatest disadvantage of doing night work is the risk of being rubbed or beaten up, in the beginnings of his job as a night taxi driver, Cătălin needed to learn how the business works, which jobs are worthy to accept from the Mini Cab office, and how some bosses behave like with the newly joined night drivers. He recollects,

The fact is, I have been working nights as a Taxi driver since September 2011. In the beginning, I worked in a different office 3 months. I left that office because of the owner. The owner was from Taliban and used to give me difficult and very poorly paid jobs. I give you an example, a job in Barking for £12 or an address he couldn't find easily even with the GPS.

Although, he liked where the office was place and that most of the jobs were good he could not continue working there because the boss became unreasonable. Cătălin learnt the business very fast and changed the office, but he has other difficulties to confront.

Walthamstow is the area where the minicab office I am based at. It's a dangerous area. Taxi drivers know that many customers have knives on them. That's why I don't argue at night with those who runaway.' Cătălin says that 'I have been robbed by black people.' He smiles, 'it's funny, but... it's always the black ones who run and don't pay the cab.' He told me that 'It happened to me at least 25-30 times since I am a minicab driver (sometimes 1-2 a week). I tell you how they do it, they get out of

the cab first. Then, they pretend to look in their pockets and run. I know colleagues from Pakistan who were rubbed, then tied to trees and abandoned

On one hand, he says, *'The advantage of working nights, he says, is that the traffic is less and it's paid better.'* He tells me that he used to take home around £90-100 per 12h nightshift. *'It's also interesting to work nights. The people are different at night - they are more cautious, stranger'*, he says. ... He pauses, reluctant to complain, but continues:

At 6-7am, I used to go to sleep when everybody in the house used to go work. At 5pm I used to wake up and at 6pm when I went to work everybody was coming home. Plus, day-sleep can't make up for the night sleep, and my social relationships were reduced to naught.

To sum it up, he tells me that working at night has more disadvantages. He describes how he felt physically and mentally during that period when he was working regularly, the graveyard shifts.

I felt like a zombie or like 'fata de traseu' (on-street prostitute).

I felt I was out of reality.

I felt extremely tired at the end of every nightshift.

Nowadays, it is not so difficult for him because he works past midnight only if he is busy, and that means he works till 2-3am. Otherwise, he finishes about 1am. And on those nights when he's not so busy he goes home and spends some time with his girlfriend. The downside is that his income has reduced to £10-£15 per shift after paying all the expenses (petrol, Mini Cab office fees). Yet, every evening he drives out his mini cab, switches on his work mobile, his GPS is tuned in and he is waiting for jobs coming via the mobile from the Mini Cab office. He says, almost sadly that

Romanians are a very cheaply paid option and that's why they get the jobs. Even so, London will survive without its migrant night workers.

Notes from the night fieldwork¹²²:

Then his manager Rasheed came to say hello to us. We had a very long conversation with him. He was very talkative, he seemed actually very eager to talk to us, he really seized the opportunity to be interviewed by us. We touched on all sorts of issues: the hotel business being a night business, about working at night ... Rasheed was positive about nocturnal work, about the night economy in general, because it is very good for the

¹²² Partly carried out with Nightlaboratory project in London

economy, you keep the youth of the street, people will have jobs, etc. He was not really for a kind of Dutch situation, which I told him about, where all shops have to close on Sundays for instance.

Labouring at night: you have to sacrifice something

'In order to accomplish something you have to give up something.' – Esther, 52, night nurse ¹²³

For Esther, the relationships with her friends are above her need of sleep. Every morning when she returns from work she sacrifices a few hours of her sleep to call her friends and check on how they are doing.¹²⁴

The condition is, at least for the beginning to suffer and sacrifice, and then to make it. It's not something bad for your own character - you learn to make sacrifices, and some plan for the future. At least for those who prefer it this way!

Rică's reference to sacrifice is an illustration of a self-development journey leading towards an improvement of character through sacrifice and building of life experience, such as planning the future. He considers that *'in order to overcome certain difficulties in life one must be prepared.'* What do you mean by being prepared, I enquired. He replied, *'I think that who is prepared can overcome these difficulties. Prepare, as in terms of being professionally prepared to in order to get opportunities for better career.'* I find Mihai's resilient attitude of similar relevance. Mihai says that night work is no different than day work.

If I adapt there is not such great difference. In the first day, you know, I feel it's hard to do a nightshift, in the end we are made to sleep at night and work during the day. I don't think [night work] is something unusual, to affect us, it is just something conjectural, but not a big deal. I, at least, can't understand those who do it for a life time, like security and bouncers – for them this is a job. That is the nature of their job. But otherwise, it's enough to adapt. No-one can force you to work nights. It is a career choice. If you follow a goal you have to do things like that ... for a while. If you want to learn something, a particular job, you have to do nightshift

Being a night labourer, as shown above by Rică and Mihai involves sacrifice, dedication and resilience in achieving personal goals, such as gaining knowledge on the Asian trading market or planning the future by commencing a MBA degree. In Rică's case the specific difficulties at the time of the interview revolved around work restrictions, which prevented him from searching for better work opportunities. At the time Rică and I had these conversations he had been working in the hotel as night auditor/hotel receptionist for 8 months. He told me then that

¹²³ Ibid, p. 79.

¹²⁴ Ibid, p. 79.

The best thing is that I have some time to do other things. What I liked was that by working nightshifts I could make other plans during the day time. For example, the MBA course that I am doing. Also, it works well in case you want to discover other ways to develop a career. The disadvantages are that nightshifts are very tiring for the body. If I wouldn't have other plans (like the MBA course) or get busy with a different project during the day I wouldn't do nightshifts.

I say it prevented him then because whilst I was writing-up this study, Rică and I met once accidentally in the University of London library where he was working toward finalising some course work for his MBA degree. He told me that he quit the night job. He said that he couldn't work nights anymore since he started the MBA. Moreover, since he had completed one full year of contracted employment with the company he worked at, it gave him eligibility to apply for the blue card, to allow him more working hours and better work opportunities in the field of economics and during the day, not nights.

Rică and Mihai share the same determination in achieving different goals. They also echoed each other's reactions when I asked them to describe their outlook on nightshifts versus dayshifts. Rică explains that

The night work is very different. First, it depends on the sector. The work I do involves auditing and less of the things done during the day, like check-in/out of the hotel. At night, we are responsible to check the work done in the day to make rectifications, which is less visible during the day. ... The question is a bit difficult. ... He takes some time to think. ... So, at night we do auditing, reports, and during the day the rest of the team do the operational part of the business (hotelier industry). We are responsible to make the corrections of the mistakes done through the day. This helps to run the business smoother during the day

Mihai echoes this and describes how greatly nightshifts differ from dayshifts. In his field, natural disasters, such as the Tsunami that took place in March 2011, have global impact on the market trends at the global level. In this case, the London's Stock Exchange. When that happens, extra night workers are called in to back up the usual night staff.

It depends, I don't think so. Sometimes I am busier at night than in the day. For example, when there was the Tsunami, in Japan, it was a horrible night, because in my job the Asian market is everything. It was terrible. We needed to call extra staff to cover the night-shift requirements that night. So, it depends on what events are going on. If something happens in Asia and it affects other financial markets. It also depends if you have more clients in America. Maybe for that you are freer during the night. If the clients are from Asia, a night-shift can be more complicated than day one. It depends of

many aspects. But the examples I gave you are from my particular field. Although, I know of some friends who if they have a big work load and need to stay up all night, they will do it. They will not go to bed.

The work night shifters do depends on several factors, such as the industry type, the level of skills required (night taxi driver or night city trader), the environment (closed offices/reception or crowded/public areas), and frequency of their work (temporary, permanent or casual). 'My brother is an underground worker', says Cătălin. He works from 22:00 – 04:00. He used to do both night and day shifts. Not anymore.'

Advantages and Disadvantages of working nightshifts

'No one is normal who comes in [the Cheyenne Diner] at night.' – Fatima, 33, night waitress¹²⁵

As the list below shows, Cătălin pointed out earlier that the advantages of working nightshifts are outweighed by disadvantages. Researchers such as Will Norman¹²⁶ carried out an ethnographic study in London throughout 2009-2010, with over 50 people taking part in the research. He found that there are 'growing dangers of working at night.' Those ones that I enumerated in the list below have been mentioned by some, but not all participants in this ethnographic study. Here are some of the key *advantages* and *disadvantages* of working nightshifts:

List 1: Key advantages and disadvantages of working night shifts

Advantages

- ✓ *Possibility to study day time*
- ✓ *Discover other ways to develop a career*
- ✓ *Interesting*
- ✓ *There is less traffic and it's paid better*
- ✓ *Helps running the business smoother during the day*
- ✓ *I have some time to do other things*

Disadvantages

- ✗ *Health concerns*
- ✗ *Tiredness*
- ✗ *Dangerous*
- ✗ *'Nightshifts are anti-social hours'*
- ✗ *'Suffering from isolation'*
 - ✗ *'Cannot joining the team for drinks or parties'*
 - ✗ *'Not isolated from night staff, but from meeting day staff hardly at all'*

¹²⁵ Ibid, p. 219.

¹²⁶ Ibid.

- ✗ *'Exclusive'*
- ✗ *'It is a kind of self-imposed isolation'*
- ✗ *'Is very lonely working at nights'*
- ✗ *'Very stressful'*
- ✗ *'Time passes by very slowly'*
- ✗ *'It's out of the eyes of the world'*
- ✗ *'There are limited opportunities to be promoted'*
- ✗ *'I'm restricted. I can only go to the cinema in the afternoon'*
- ✗ *'People who work nightshifts are like a 'second world'*

Some are re-occurring ones. On one hand, there are less positive consequences from working nights. They seem to show a functional role, i.e. night work helps complements day-time business agenda or that they are more goals oriented (e.g. day study, developing career, better pay rate). On the other hand, the negative consequences are more than the positive ones. Besides of the obvious health hazards¹²⁷ and anti-social nature of night work¹²⁸, one of the difficulties participants found it hard to cope with during nightshifts was isolation – either from other day staff or because at night there are less people up and working. Isolation occurs in various forms (self-isolation, exclusiveness, loneliness).

There are two key disadvantages mentioned below, that characterise working nightshifts as something that *'it's out of the eyes of the world'* or a *'second world'*. These two expressions were used by two different participants, Rică and Cătălin, respectively. They were working in different, but connected service sectors. Hotels use mini cabs for their own clients, and vice versa. What I think might echo in both participants is their young age; both in their late 20's. More importantly, the duration of working nights is almost the same. At the time of interviewing, Rică had been a night worker for 8 months and Cătălin 9 months. Unlike Mihai who has been in GB for almost 12 years or Leon who told me he was 'fresh off the boat' with only 2-3 months in GB. Perhaps, this indicates that around there may be a heightened vulnerability to problems such as isolation experienced in conjunction with night work. Also, due to their young age associated with heightened activity and stimulation they may find it particularly difficult to work in isolation when night time passes slowly and without much human contact or action. However, 'much of the night economy is invisible to us'¹²⁹ therefore people working as part of the night night economy might just feel 'unseen and ill-used.'¹³⁰

¹²⁷ Ibid.

¹²⁸ Barbara Ellen, 'Unseen and Ill-Used – the Plight of Night Workers', *The Guardian*
<<http://www.guardian.co.uk/commentisfree/2012/jul/29/barbara-ellen-plight-of-shift-workers>>

¹²⁹ Ibid, p. 10.

¹³⁰ Ibid.

Hence, why I think there might be a correlation between young night workers, like Rică and Cătălin feeling invisible from the work scene, unfulfilled due to lack of opportunities to be promoted or not finding it challenging enough to sit and wait for night to cross the frontier into the day.

All four participants however, have given clear indications that the night work they were carrying out was only for a 'period', in 'conjuncture' with other plans and serving a much greater purpose. Despite the level of skill they needed in their jobs, these four male participants were in their late 20's to late 30's, very focused on higher goals and well-intended to achieve them. The more concrete example comes from Rică's immediate experience, which I have mentioned earlier when I described my accidental meeting with him. In my view, although accidental the meeting served the purpose of a brief follow-up, gathering evidence about his current circumstances, which suffice to say it fulfils my position as a participant observer to take notes of what has been said and what has been done. Ultimately, this criterion is a crucial element in anthropological research.

In Rică's context, he did say in our conversations that all Romanians who fulfil the criteria of working one year with an employer they can apply for a blue card and thus enhance their chances to better work opportunities, which is exactly what Rică has planned. He has taken a step upward in the context of social mobility. Next however, I will elaborate my interpretations and offer an interpretation or a 'version of the truth' of the findings described in the results section.

Discussion and conclusions

This chapter discusses the findings as follows: first re-summarises the main findings and offers an interpretation of the findings. It also considers any methodological limitations that may have compromised the results, the implications of this investigation, and concludes with some modest proposals for future possibilities of research.

The research findings show that in an age of Europeanisation, Romania's social and political decay pushes its nationals to travel to work and live in other European countries, in order to fulfil possibilities otherwise unachievable in their home country. The factors that influence Romanians' day-to-day lives abroad vary from: pre-migration trajectories and working lives in Romania, networking in order to find employment abroad, the ways in which they negotiate hardships, family life with work commitments and the goals they aspire in their careers for which some of the participants needed to sacrifice. The focus in this study has been on the persons who migrate from Romania, a peripheric society, to a mature capitalist society, such as Great Britain. More specifically, concerned with migrants working nightshifts as part of London's night economy.

The most salient findings show that in the context of Romania's accession to the EU in 2007, its nationals have received differential access and restricted rights to work on the EU job markets. In this respect, the free movement of workers from Romania (and Bulgaria) has been restricted through a 7-year transition arrangement, time in which many Romanians became disillusioned because they have been excluded from this fundamental principle of the Treaty, which applies since 2006 to all EU nationals, but clearly this has not been the case for them. Second, and in the same context, the decision to invite Romania into the EU without giving its full membership was a mistake, as Keith Vaz, MP commented to the author. Third,

the study highlights existing paradoxes between the idealised notions of freedom of movement of workers and the realities in day-to-day lives of Romanians living in GB.

Other themes and sub-themes elicited from the combined methods of field observations and semi-structured interviews include negotiating dangerous night customers using minicab services and sacrifice sleep at night in order to pursue other goals during the day, such as attending courses at day universities. Cumulating debt bondage in order to finance travelling for work is another theme illustrating that in the process of migrancy, some benefit from that whilst others become debt ridden.

In line with the Marxist principle of struggles between the classes, by isolating this instance for analysis, for example, cumulating debt bondage to travel and work abroad, when one looks closer what one finds is that underneath the generic features of migrancy, such as pre-migration background or networking, people are prepared to renounce to their social status, i.e. a project manager with a degree accepts a night job in a bar. Others cumulate debts in order to finance their travelling to work abroad. During this process however, those who sell these services (e.g. employment agencies) profit at the expense of migrants, and in cases like Rică's, some do not honour the contracts. Migrants such as Rică, from the 'struggling class' cumulate debts that may take years to repay their family members, friends or worse other agencies in the chain that sell these services.

One of the methodological limitations of this study may be reflected in the fact that participants are only men and a sample of only four. However, this investigation is not aimed at generating generalising, representative concepts. For that reason, the size of the sample is less important. However, why are there so few women working nights?

Will Norman found that 'the night workforce is predominately male (55% male, 45% female). This imbalance may be due to the nature of the job (i.e. security at night being male dominated). This may change in the future as the night service expands and more women are likely to be working at night, but currently men are predominant in jobs during the night. A night manager said during a field observation that at Tesco it is mostly men who work at night because they need brute force for carrying heavy loads and stocking up shelves.

In the light of comparisons with other scholarly literature, for example Norman's¹³¹ study on British night workers, similarities, differences and contrasting aspects are discussed below. Norman carried out 50 interviews with British night workers, but not with Eastern Europeans who live in GB. In contrast, this investigation is focused on Eastern Europeans travelling to London, which enlarges the concept that London is a global city and therefore its night economy needs maintenance around-the-clock to the extent that in an era of Globalisation and Europeanisation migrants are pushed to travel from peripheric locations to core, global ones. The Migration and World Systems theories discussed earlier support this phenomenon and explain that disruptions and dislocations are the effect of capitalist expansion into non-capitalist societies.

The perspective from which Norman provides recommendations is one based on the negatives of working nights. In a more balanced approach, in this study participants enumerated positive as well as negative consequences of working nights. Among the positives are: remuneration is better at night, traffic is less convoluted, allowing study time in the day, and learning specificities of a certain type of work. However, this study engages with the current public debates in Western European countries on the supposed inflow of working

¹³¹ Ibid.

migrants coming from Eastern Europe and threatening to overtake the jobs of the people in the destination countries (i.e. GB).

In conclusion, Romania's accession to the EU has created some, but not all possible opportunities to allow Romanians, as with other Eastern Europeans, to travel and work freely. In short, Romanians are 'neither here, nor there' – they can travel, but with limitations. They can work, but with even stricter limitations. These constraints create further vulnerabilities for Romanians whilst abroad.

Romania is still under the watchdog scrutiny of the EC for not fighting corruption and preserving democratic principles. In comparison to the ideal European citizen Romanians are still pushed to leave their country and fulfil their imagined possibilities elsewhere in Europe. Its nationals become the underclass of the EU, not quite prospering in their home country and merely struggling to survive in other parts of Europe.

Some modest proposals

7-year transition strategy for Romania and Bulgaria comes to an end in December 2013. This will be crucial for both these countries citizens as the restrictions against their free movement to work in other European countries will end, weather GB and other old member states will like it or not.

Therefore, as a modest proposal for further research one recommendation of this research would be to follow-up the participants in this study, enquire into their circumstances post transition to find out if their life experiences have changed and what ways.

Furthermore, raising awareness of the dangers that night workers face, such as accidents happening on the way home at the end of a night shift or the negotiations they need to carry out with harmful individual whilst on night duty. One example is the night taxi driver who has been a victim of robbery at least a dozen of times.

Besides raising awareness amongst those in charge of the instruments of legislation, efforts should be made to raise awareness of the risks night workers face themselves, which as research show is alarmingly low amongst the night workers. Researchers should become active in promoting such awareness through programs set either in the workplaces or in communities where there is a preponderance of night workers. To name but a few of the advices and recommendations that would benefit this category of workers, not neglecting relationships, getting enough sleep before night shifts, make aware their own GP that they do regular night work.

Lastly, at the EU and national levels, it is recommended that improved legislation to protect night workers should be high on the agenda. Currently, such legislation exists and protects night workers under the European Working Time Directive not to work longer than eight hours within a 24-hour period. Whether this is respected and enforce in the work places is a different question altogether. However, the consumerist behaviour has exacerbated since the Industrial Revolution with its heavily mechanised processes has allowed for the extension of work around the clock, i.e. night work will be on the expansion to sustain the growing night economy. More studies could explore such venues for further research.

Appendix One: Short Biographies of the Four Participants

Rică, the day student and night hotel auditor/receptionist

Rică is 28, an ambitious young man from Bucovina region in North Romania. He was born in the same city as Mihai, but they did not know of each other. He finished his BA in Economics in Romania and after he finished it, he went to the US where he studied at a Bible College while he did an internship in the Hotelier Industry. Then, he worked illegally for one year. This happened in 2007 – 2009. Once he arrived in GB, Rică was constrained by legislation to work only 20 hours per week and after a few interviews he only found night work. He saw it as a sacrifice in order to develop a career during day time.

Leon, the barman ‘traveller on this planet’

Leon is in his late 20's and he finished Polytechnics in Romania and started masters in Analytical Philosophy, but only did two months of the course. In the pre-migration period, he worked as a Project Manager, in Romania. He was very critical of the Romanian Government. He had no trust in it and was very dissatisfied with how things were going under this government. *‘But this is not, he tells me, the reason I left.’* Leon left because he had in plan to continue his higher education with a Masters at Cambridge.

Mihai, the night city trader specialised on the Asian market

Mihai is in his late 30's and was born and lived in Bucovina, like Rică. When Mihai left Romania 12 years ago some of his family members were against him leaving, others supported him. He left Romania because he studied finances in Romania and that the place to be for those who did finance is London. That's the reason why he came to London. Although, he had the chance to travel, London is the place he liked and wanted to work. He works in a trading company in London and does 5 nights out of 7 in a team of mixed nationalities.

Cătălin, the night taxi driver

Cătălin is a 29 year old Romania Roma, from Southern Romania. In Romania he worked with his father in the forest, cutting and selling wood to private home owners for the winter time. They have land and most of his life after he finished the 7th grade he worked with his father. When he arrived in GB his older brother was already working and helped him to buy the first car and paid for his minicab licence. He lives with his brothers and sisters and their mother comes and helps with their disabled brother. Cătălin says that they are 3 white children and 3 black/dark children. Their father lives in Romania.

Appendix Two: Semi-structured Interview Questions

Semi-structured interview questions: addressed in Romanian and translated into English

- 1) How long have you been living in London?
- 2) Are you living in London with family or on your own?
- 3) Do you have family in Romania?
- 4) Do you keep in touch with the family there?
- 5) What does your family say about you living and working in London?
- 6) Do you intend to sponsor any family member to come and work in the UK?
- 7) How do you see the work restrictions imposed to Romanian citizens in the UK?
 - a) Are these measures encouraging? Beneficial? Or discouraging?

Questions about Working at Night:

- 1) How long have you been working nightshifts?
 - a) How long have you been a night taxi driver for?
- 2) What motivated you to work nights?
 - a) Variation of the same question: why do you work nightshifts?
 - b) How long do you intend to carry on working nights?
- 3) Does night work differ from day work? And if yes, in what ways?
 - a) Could you give me some examples?
- 4) Do you think that London's night economy needs migrant night workers?
- 5) What are the advantages/disadvantages of working nights?
- 6) What is your routine like after you finished a nightshift?
- 7) What are your nightshifts colleagues like?

References

- (OECD), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, *International Migration Outlook 2012* OECD Publishing, 2012).
- Agency, UK Border, 'Bulgarian and Romanian nationals', UK Border Agency, (2012)
<<http://www.ukba.homeoffice.gov.uk/eucitizens/bulgaria-romania/>> [Accessed 25.08. 2012].
- Agustín, Laura María, *Sex at the margins : migration, labour markets and the rescue industry* (London ; New York: Zed Books, 2007).
- Andreev, Svetlozar A., 'The Unbearable Lightness of Membership: Bulgaria and Romania After the 2007 EU Accession', *Communist and Post-Communist Studies*, 42 (2009), 375-93.
- Appadurai, Arjun *Modernity at large: cultural dimensions of globalization* (United States: University of Minnesota Press, 1996).
- Back, Les, *The art of listening* (Oxford: Berg, 2007).
- Becker, Howard Saul, *Telling about society, Chicago guides to writing, editing, and publishing* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2007).
- Berth Danermark, Mats Ekström, Lisolette Jakobsen and Jan Ch. Karlsson, *Explaining Society: Critical realism in the social sciences* (Abingdon, Oxon, UK: Routledge, 2002).
- Blaikie, Norman, *Approaches to Social Inquiry* (Cambridge: Polity, 2000).
- Bojkov, Victor D., 'Neither Here, Not There: Bulgaria and Romania in Current European Politics', *Communist and Post-Communist Studies*, 37 (2004), 509-22.
- Boogaarts, Simone, 'Claiming Your Place at Night: Turkish Dance Parties in The Netherlands', *Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 34 (8) (2008), 1283-300.
- Bouma, Gary D., et al., *A handbook of social science research*. 2nd ed. / Gary D. Bouma, G. B. J. Atkinson. edn (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1995).
- Bryman, Alan, *Social Research Methods* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2001).
- Commission, European, 'Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council. On Progress in Romania under the Cooperation and Verification Mechanism.', (Brussels: European Commission 2008).
- Crang, Mike, and Cook, Ian, *Doing ethnographies* (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2007).
- Crotty, Micahel, *The Foundations of Social Research: Meaning and Perspective in the Research Process* (London: Sage, 1998).
- Directorate General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion, European Commission, 'Workers from new EU member countries - transitional arrangements', ed. by European, Commission (<http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=466&langId=en>: Directorate General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion, 2012).
- Duijzings, Gerlachlus, *Religion and the politics of identity in Kosovo* (London: Hurst & Company, 2000).

- Ellen, Barbara 'Unseen and Ill-Used – the Plight of Night Workers', *The Guardian*, (2012) <<http://www.guardian.co.uk/commentisfree/2012/jul/29/barbara-ellen-plaint-of-shift-workers>> [Accessed 14.08. 2012].
- Fawcett, J. T., 'Networks, Linkages, and Migration Systems', *International Migration Review*, 23 (1989), 671-80.
- Furlong, David Marsh and Paul, 'A Skin, not a Sweater: Ontology and Epistemology in Political Science', in *Theory and Methods in Political Science*, ed. by Stoker, David Marsh and Gerry (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2002).
- Gowan, Teresa, and ebrary, Inc, *Hobos, hustlers, and backsliders : homeless in San Francisco* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2010).
- Graeber, David, *Possibilities : essays on hierarchy, rebellion and desire* (Edinburgh: AK, 2007).
- Gray, Ann, *Research practice for cultural studies : ethnographic methods and lived cultures*. Reprint. edn (London: Sage, 2004).
- Grix, Johnathan, 'Introducing Students to the Generic Terminology of Social Science Research', *Politics*, 22 (2002), 175-86.
- Groff, E., and McCord, E. S., 'The role of neighborhood parks as crime generators', *Security Journal*, 25 (2012), 1-24.
- Hadfield, P., 'From threat to promise - Nightclub 'security', governance and consumer elites', *British Journal of Criminology*, 48 (2008), 429-47.
- Hammersley, Martyn, and Atkinson, Paul, *Ethnography : principles in practice*. 2nd edn (London: Routledge, 1995).
- Heywood, Andrew, *Political ideologies : an introduction*. 4th edn (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2007).
- Humphrey, Robin, et al., *Biographical research in Eastern Europe : altered lives and broken biographies* (Aldershot: Ashgate, 2003).
- Insight, Balkan, 'EU to Set Restrictions for Bulgaria, Romania Workers', *Balkan Insight*, 2012).
- Jenkins, Richard, *Social identity, Key ideas* (London ; New York: Routledge, 1996).
- King, Gary, et al., *Designing social inquiry : scientific inference in qualitative research* (Princeton, N.J. ; Chichester: Princeton University Press, 1994).
- Kreitzman, Leon, *The 24 hour society* (London: Profile, 1999).
- , *The 24 hour society : transforming time in our lives* (London: Profile, 1999).
- Lambert, Elizabeth Y., and National Institute on Drug Abuse, National Institute on Drug Abuse, *The collection and interpretation of data from hidden populations, NIDA research monograph* (Rockville MD: National Institute on Drug Abuse, 1990).
- Linde, C., *Life stories : the creation of coherence* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1993).

- Mai, Nicola 'Migrant Workers in the UK Sex Industry: Full Research Report, ESRC End of Award Report', Economic and Social Science Research Committee, 2009).
- Massey, D. S., et al., 'Theories of International Migration - A Review and Appraisal', *Population and Development Review*, 19 (1993), 431-66.
- Maynard, Mary, *Methods, practice and epistemology: The debate about feminism and research* (London: Taylor & Francis, 1994).
- Melbin, Murray, *Night as frontier : colonizing the world after dark* (New York and London: Free Press ; Collier Macmillan, 1987).
- Miller, Robert L., *Researching life stories and family histories, Introducing qualitative methods* (London: SAGE, 2000).
- Mitchell, T., 'The World as Exhibition', *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 31 (1989), 217-36.
- Nath, Suman, 'Political Economy in Anthropology ', www.blogger.co.uk, (2011) <<http://sumananthromaterials.blogspot.co.uk/2011/10/political-economy-in-anthropology.html>> [Accessed 12.08. 2012].
- Norman, Will, 'Rough Nights: The Growing Dangers of Working at Night', Young Foundation, 2011).
- Olsen, Johan P., 'The Many Faces of Europeanization', *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 40 (2002), 921-52.
- Pensions, Department for Work and, 'National Insurance Number Allocations', Department for Work and Pensions, 2012).
- Pleșu, Andrei, 'A Brutal Assault: Democracy Loses as Romania Spins out of Control', *Der Spiegel*, (2012) <<http://www.spiegel.de/international/europe/democracy-the-loser-in-romanian-power-struggle-a-843449.html>> [Accessed 01.08 2012].
- Pusca, Anca Mihaela, *Revolution, democratic transition and disillusionment : the case of Romania, Perspectives on democratic practice (Manchester, England)* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2008).
- Racoviță, Mihaela, 'Europeanization and Effective Democracy in Romania and Bulgaria', *Romanian Journal of Political Science*, 11 (2011), 28-49.
- Roberts, M., 'Planning, urban design and the night-time city: Still at the margins?', *Criminology & Criminal Justice*, 9 (2009), 487-506.
- Rowe, D., and Bavinton, N., 'Tender for the night: After-dark cultural complexities in the night-time economy', *Continuum-Journal of Media & Cultural Studies*, 25 (2011), 811-25.
- Samuels, R., 'After-dark design, night animation, and interpersonal interaction: Toward a community-security paradigm', *Journal of Architectural and Planning Research*, 22 (2005), 305-18.
- Sandhu, Sukhdev, and Artangel, *Night haunts : a journey through the London night*. 1 vols (London: Verso, 2010).

- Sassen, Saskia, *The Mobility of Labor and Capital: A Study in International Investment and Labor Flow*. 1st paperback edition. edn (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1988).
- Sharman, Russell Leigh, and Sharman, Cheryl Harris, *Nightshift NYC* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2008).
- Smith, David Marsh and Martin J., 'There is More Than One Way to do Political Science: On Different Ways to Study Policy Networks', *Political Studies*, 49 (2001), 528-41.
- Steger, Manfred B., *Globalization : a very short introduction, Very short introductions* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2003).
- Stevenson, Angus, ed., *Oxford Dictionary of English., Oxford Reference Online. University College London. 9 April 2012*
<<http://www.oxfordreference.com/views/ENTRY.html?subview=Main&entry=t140.e0276680>>
> (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010).
- UK, Român in, 'A British Member of Parliament says it! 'O spune un parlamentar britanic!' ', Român in UK, (2012) <<http://romaninuk.net/index.php>> [Accessed 25.08. 2012].
- Vermeersch, Peter, 'Roma and Mobility in the European Union', in *Roma and Traveller Inclusion in Europe. Green Questions and Answers.*, ed. by Pietarinen, Kati (Belgium: Green European Foundation and Finnish Green Cultural and Educational Centre, Visio, 2011).
- Verstraete, Ginette, *Tracking Europe: Mobility, Diaspora, and the Politics of Location* (Durham and London: Duke University Press, 2010).
- Vyas, V. Manav, et al., 'Shift Work and Vascular Events: Systematic Review and Meta-analysis', *British Medical Journal*, 345 (2012), 1-11.
- Wallerstein, Immanuel Maurice, *The Modern World-System* Academic, 1974).
- Williams, Robert, 'Night Spaces: Darkness, Deterritorialization, and Social Control', *Space and Culture*, 11 (2008), 514.
- Zlotnik, Hania, 'Empirical Identification of International Migration Systems', in *International Migration Systems: A Global Approach*, ed. by Kritz, Mary M., Lim, Lin Lean and Zlotnik, Hania (Oxford: Clarendon, 1992).